

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

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Executive Summary

This document is an update of the analysis and systematic review of best practices, technologies and applications presented in the M9 with the deliverable D2.2. The objective of this deliverable is once the final solution of the Ageing@Work project is already designed and first version of the solutions implemented ready to be deployed and evaluated, discover new solutions aimed to improve the second version of the Ageing@Work system, and have an updated pull of information to solve the possible issues during the piloting phase.

As well as we have used in the first version of this deliverable, the systematic review has been carried out using the PICO model and has allowed the selection and classification of best practices, technologies and applications, according to most common workability problems classification and domains addressed in ageing at work. Each of the solution was mapped with the corresponding UCs according to the last version of these use cases, updated in M12.

The influence of COVID-19 has also been analysed in this deliverable, in terms of types of solutions, practices but also how the COVID-19 has an influence on the affected domains, UCs and workability problems addressed.

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List of Terms and definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
AG	Aktiengesellschaft (Public Limited Company)
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANEFA	Asociación Nacional de Empresarios Fabricantes de Áridos
API	Application Program Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
dB	Decibel
DR	Design Requirement
EDA	Electrodermal activity
EEG	Electroencephalogram
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
EU	European Union
GPS	Global Positioning System
HR	Human Resources
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
N/A	Not available
NIOSH	National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OHSAS	Occupational Health and Safety Assessment Series
OS	Operating System
OWI	Older Worker Identity
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
PICO	P – Patient, Problem or Population. I – Intervention. C – Comparison, control or comparator. O – Outcome(s)
R&D	Research & Development
RQ	Research Question
SDK	Software Development Kit
SOS	Save Our Souls
SW	Software
UC	Use Case
UX	User Experience
VR	Virtual Reality
WAI	Work Ability Index
WP	Work Package

Table 1 Definitions

1. Introduction

This document is an update of the D2.2 Supportive motivating and persuasive approaches tools and metrics, submitted in M9. This document presented the up to now state of art of smart working and living environment solutions and tools that are used to maintain workability and well-being.

Since the submission of that deliverable, important events have occurred with a high impact on work, social relationships and health. When the COVID-19 pandemic hit Europe in March 2020, an unprecedented phenomenon occurred. More than 250 million people were into lockdown, and only essential activities were allowed. This situation forced millions of workers to work from home and for those that was not possible because of the nature of their work, they had to change their workflows to adapt to new security restrictions and protocols.

The COVID-19 has forced a technology disruption in every of the living areas, especially at work and faster adoption of automation and AI, reducing the need of workload involved mainly in routine tasks, in a need of reducing the social contact. This has opened a new opportunity to aged workers since they can benefit from automatization in the more physical demanding task, while they can use their experience on other tasks, reducing in this way the impact of hard-working conditions on their health. On the other hand, it is expected that this technological uptake brings also the need of switching occupations, facilitating occupational shifts by focusing on the skills workers needs and retraining.

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable complements the systematic review of best practices, technologies and tools performed in M9 (D2.2: Supportive motivating and persuasive approaches tools and metrics) with new components widely used in industries and factories, taking into account the extensive usage of virtual work due to COVID-19 outbreak.

The systematic review was performed according to the methodology proposed in D2.2, based on the PICO framework, adding a new category oriented to discover the adaptation due to COVID-19 with special focus in aged-workers. With this work, this deliverable aims to provide new requirements and best practices to be incorporated into the Ageing@Work system, in order to adapt the use cases and the real setting applicability of the solutions.

1.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

As well as the previous version of this deliverable, the current document is directly related to the work performed in the WP4 and WP5 of this project. But, on contrary to the previous one, this is also related to the WP7, in particular with the pilot deployment and evaluation of the system, since the lessons learned with this systematic review will influence on the pilot setting up.

The current deliverable is directly related to the work that will be performed in T4.1 on the open framework for worker activity and behavioural tracking, and in the Ageing@Work Virtual Coach WP5.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable consists of four sections plus annexes. Section 1 “Introduction” describes the scope of the deliverable, its relationship with other activities within the project and the structure of the document itself. Section 2 “Benchmarking methodology and criteria” summarizes the methodology followed for performing the systematic audit and the templates created for this purpose. Section 3, “Results” presents the results of the analysis, identifying the most relevant parts of the applications, technologies and best practices, such as a brief description, the domains related to each of the results and the use cases to which they could be applied. The 4th section, “Overall conclusions of benchmarking”, shows the conclusions and in the annexes I to III, we can see all the applications, tools, technologies and best practices analysed.

2. Benchmarking methodology and criteria

The PICO Model described in detail in section 2 Benchmarking methodology and criteria of the D2.2, provides the necessary framework to guide the research in a specific patient's problem. In this case, the adapted research questions were the same ones used in the previous version of this deliverable and included in table 2, just a reminder:

Table 2 Ageing@Work PICO design questions

What population are we interested in?	Active workers over 50 years old. No restriction about the work type
What kind of interventions are we interested in?	Any kind of tools, technologies, adaptations or best practices that cover the main domains and areas of interest (Policy for older workers, Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement), Improving productivity and workability, Healthy habits programs, Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms
Would the study need a <i>comparison</i> group?	Comparison could be with those workers or companies that do not use any kind of compensatory mechanism, tool, technology or best practice
What are the <i>outcomes</i> we are interested in?	Improvement documented in the following areas: Learning and cognitive functions, sensory ability, physical ability, psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) and workability (including promotion and workplace design; redeployment and transition to retirement

Using these research questions, the research team was able to use the common templates designed for the previous version of the deliverable (and included in Criteria for a review), where they have collected the relevant data for the analysis. In this case, the search terms were the same included in the previous version (included in the Table 3), plus COVID-19, lockdown, pandemic, restrictions and social distance.

Table 3 Search words

Career advancement	Work ability	Aged worker (aging at work)
Stay at work	Compensation mechanisms	Work limitation
Early retirement	Disability	Functional decline
COVID-19	Lockdown	Pandemic
Safety restrictions	Social distance	

The following electronic databases were searched; Web of Science, Sociological Abstract, PsycINFO (OVID), American Business Index (ABI) Inform. All peer-reviewed literature was included, including non-English citations. To identify current applications of interest also the Google Play site and the App Store site of Apple have been searched using the same terms as in literature.

After completion of the searches and exclusion of duplicate results, two independent researchers from the UPM made the initial screening of included publications based on the review of titles and abstracts. Full papers and documentation of the final list of elements were obtained and distributed among the research team to be reviewed for quality and data extracted, according to the distributed template. In addition to the computerized search, references from included studies were also checked (i.e., snowball method) to ensure that no relevant publications has been omitted.

As the methodological approach described in the D2.2 ensure, the benchmarked best practices, tools, technological and practical cases, cover the dimensions of age management in Europe in five? domains:

- Policy for older workers, aimed to improve interpersonal and intergenerational communication at work,
- Increasing job retention aimed to enhance workability and well-being based on retraining and workspace adaptability,
- Improving productivity and workability based on physical and mental health programs promotion,
- Healthy habit programs, mainly focused on leisure educational programs and early prevision interventions and finally,
- Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms focused on adaption of the working environment to specific chronic illness and diseases.

More information about these domains and the subsequent methodology is available in the section 2 of the D2.2, as well as the structure of the used templates to collect the information.

3. Results

In total 45 templates were filled. 4 were not taken into consideration due to the lack of focus on the Ageing@Work direct and indirect goals. The 41 final templates can be found in the Annex I, II and III. Every one of the elements was analysed, classified according to the usefulness of the tools, technology, applications, practices, methodologies, or best practice in each of the final version of the use cases delivered at M12.

3.1 Tools and technologies

Following sections present a short summary of the main characteristics of the technologies, applications and tools included in the benchmarking. The explanation of each of them tries to include the most relevant information for the Ageing@Work purposes. In addition, in the case of technologies widely used in research and real-life environment to support workers, an extra analysis was done in order to identify the main characteristics, differences and other elements of interests that facilitate the future development of Ageing@Work final solution.

3.1.1 Technologies

As it was defined in the D2.2, the technologies to improve the workability are those that serve to increase or improve the worker's capability. Table 5 includes a general description of the technologies included in this benchmark, while Table 6 links the benefits of the technology with the specific domains and use cases in the project. Finally, some graphs classify the technologies analysed per UCs and per domain of use. References of the included technologies are in Annexes section. The first one is highlighted since it addresses specific challenges due to COVID-19.

Table 4 Technologies

Name	Summary
Applying Blockchain Technology to Address the Crisis of Trust during the COVID-19 Pandemic	The widespread death and disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic has revealed deficiencies of existing institutions regarding the protection of human health and well-being. Both the lack of accurate and timely data and pervasive misinformation are causing an increasing harm and growing tension between data privacy and public health concerns. Blockchain technology, with its distributed trust networks and cryptography-based security, may provide solutions to data-related trust problems.
IIM LEAD	Age-related changes to human working abilities are addressed as following in the IIM LEAD factory: a training for ergonomics and age-appropriate workplace design is being currently developed.
easyfaM	Platform with various instructions and trainings on how to reconcile family (with children) and work and how to create family-friendly company structures.

N.I.Te	N.I.Te provides innovative software technologies for automatic document processing, especially handwritten documents, both off-line from static images, and on-line from handwritten coordinates acquired by several devices.
DearEmployee	DearEmployee is a corporate health platform that supports companies in creating healthy and motivating working conditions for their employees (mental health focus).
Userlane	Userlane is a no-code Digital Adoption Platform that is designed to maximize software adoption by allowing anyone to master any software instantly. This is made possible with a step-by-step interactive guidance technology and an on-demand Virtual Assistant that offers contextual and tailored support to software users whenever they need it. This solution can be used both for employee onboarding and training (enterprise digital adoption) as well as customer onboarding and self-service (for software vendors).

A total of 6 new technologies have been added to the 13 previous one, delivered in the first version of the present document. The distribution per domain of these new 6 technologies is represented in Figure 5, with the majority of technologies for Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability.

Figure 1 Distribution of technologies per domain, i.e., Domain 1: Policy for older workers, Domain 2 Increasing job retention, Domain 3 Improving productivity and workability, Domain 4: Healthy habits, Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms.

These domains distribution is also appreciated in the analysed technologies distribution per use cases, with a clear majority of applications found in UC3: Support Musculoskeletal problems which is related with physical status and UC4: Support health and well-being which is related with well-being.

The graphical distribution of technologies is represented per pilot site in the Figure 2.

Figure 2 Distribution of technologies per UCs in each of the pilots: i.e., UC1 Checklist platform, UC2 Participatory work orchestration, UC3 Support for musculoskeletal problem, UC4 Supporting health and well-being virtual coach, UC5: Knowledge exchange platform and intergenerational collaboration support, UC6: Productivity enhancement tool, UC7: Emergency/Panic button

Finally, detailed information about these apps and tools are included in Table 5.

Table 5 Selected technologies mapping with Ageing@work specific domains and pilot use cases

	Problems addressed	Domain	UCs	Relevant comments for Ageing@Work
Applying Blockchain Technology to Address the Crisis of Trust during the COVID-19 Pandemic	Physical ability	Domain 4	UC2 UC5 UC6	Blockchain relies on a distributed, robust, secure, privacy-preserving, and immutable record framework that can positively transform the nature of trust, value sharing, and transactions.
IIM LEAD	Sensory ability Physical ability Psychology/Mental abilities	Domain 5	UC2 UC3 UC4 UC5 UC6	It could be an extension of the VR and AR tools in the future
easyfaM	Learning, cognitive functions	Domain 2 Domain 3 Domain 4	UC6 UC4	Many of the concepts, even those that relate more to the private sphere, have similarities to common management or working methods or are based on them, it could improve the private life management proposed by the A@W system
N.I.Te	Learning, cognitive functions Physical ability Psychology/Mental abilities	Domain 1 Domain 3 Domain 5	UC2 UC5 UC4	
DearEmployee	Psychology/Mental abilities	Domain 3 Domain 4	UC4	Maybe COVID-19 approach could be useful to address some of the validation issues.
Userlane	Learning cognitive	Domain 1 Domain 2 Domain 3 Domain 5	UC3 UC5 UC6	Influence on the training programs included in the project

3.1.2 Final results of technologies

A total of 21 technologies useful for the Ageing@Work purposes have been analysed in the T2.1. Just to summarize the work done in D2.2 and D2.7, the following figures represent the domains and use case covered by the total of the technologies analysed in both deliverables. For more detailed information about the best practices, one can refer to D2.2 Supporting motivating and persuasive approaches tools and metrics, v1 section 3.1 Technologies.

Figure 3 presents the final results of the technologies included in the benchmarking done in the corresponding task. The domain more frequently addressed is Domain 3 while the domain less addressed is the Domain 1. The latter is the domain that concerns the “Policy for older works”, for which it is shown that the rare reference reveals the difficulties to involve decision makers in the process of addressing aging problem at work.

Figure 3 Total number of Technologies (D2.1 and D2.7) included in the benchmarking addressed domains i.e., Domain 1: Policy for older workers, Domain 2 Increasing job retention, Domain 3 Improving productivity and workability, Domain 4: Healthy habits, Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms.

Furthermore, the following figure represents, the use cases most affected use cases by these best practices, taking into account the results of both deliverables. In this case, UC4: Supporting health and well-being virtual coach and UC6: Productivity enhancement tools are the most suitable to benefit from the proposed technologies.

Figure 4 Use Cases distribution of the technologies analyzed in D2.1 and D2.7 UC1 Checklist platform, UC2 Participatory work orchestration, UC3 Support for musculoskeletal problem, UC4 Supporting health and well-being virtual coach, UC5: Knowledge exchange platform and intergenerational collaboration support, UC6: Productivity enhancement tool, UC7: Emergency/Panic button

3.1.3 Tools and applications

In this section, tools and applications to increase the workability are analysed. In case of tools, we remember that we have considered any type of software that facilitates the execution of a task and in case of applications we have thoroughly examined various tools and applications that the worker can use for specific and well-defined purposes.

In order to illustrate the usefulness of each tool and application, we have included **Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.**, with their general description and a summary of the benefits of them regarding Ageing@Work purposes. Besides, their elements are linked with main domains and use cases addressed by the project. Moreover, some graphs classify the tools and application analysed per UCs and per domain of use. References of the included tools and applications are in Annexes section. Finally, we have added 22 different solutions with especial impact on Ageing@Work solution, 3 of them (coloured in grey) direct related to COVID-19 situation.

Table 6 Tools and applications

Name	Summary
Comfy / SafeWorkspace	Manages office presence of employees in COVID-19 times
BlogIn	BlogIn is a simple internal blog and knowledge sharing platform for teams of all sizes. Internal blog is a perfect tool to share internal news, archive knowledge, boost collaboration and improve internal communication

Muscle & Motion	It is a professional app for acquiring advanced knowledge on strength training, stretching anatomy and posture during yoga learning how to prevent common mistakes in order to reduce risk of injury (including concrete reasons for why these mistakes occur), and deeply understanding the anatomy of all human muscles in the most visual way.
Diet&Training by Ann	Diet & Training by Ann Lewandowska is an individually tailored fit diet and simple training. Simple diet - the person chooses what to eat. Training plan for everyone - exercises on various difficulty levels
Neuropil	The Neuropil layer is an open source solution that assures the stable communication between machines and applications. It is a c-library, which is locally installed and embedded into a company's own application or devices. The lean messaging library is developed with two layers of encryption (transport and end-to-end) and it gives each system a digital entity to avoid unauthorized access
PIPEFORCE	PIPEFORCE is an easy-to-use and freely scalable platform based on Kubernetes in order to be able to develop, link and automate business workflows uniformly in a container environment. With this platform, companies can migrate their services step by step
Smartfence	Smartfence is an Information Security training and awareness platform that develops safe habits for end users
SmartWe	It is an app-based CRM Cloud solution for small and medium-sized companies
Spatial	Spatial is an AR workspace app In AR mode, the Spatial mobile app allows the user to beam avatars of your friends or team-mates right into your living room to collaborate in the real space.
TrackLean	TrackLean is a Software as a Service (SaaS) solution for the electronic signing of contract documents online
Valarea	It is a visual collaboration software that enables sharing, noting and presenting digital content in real-time from any device. Projects can be organized in folders called "workspaces", allowing to archive and sync files, media and meeting sessions on all devices.
LabsLand	LabsLand connects users (schools, universities and individual users) with real laboratories available somewhere else on the Internet.
VIDSigner	VIDSigner (one of the Validated ID solutions) is an electronic signature service adapted to both face-to-face and remote situations, combining cryptography and biometrics to offer a secure way to electronically sign documents and contracts with full legal validity.
Files.fm	Cloud storage and synchronizing tool
OpenClassrooms	Online education platform for vocational training, providing courses in IT, technology, entrepreneurship, and digital skills
Jobs@Skills	Platform for further training measures
LifeSignals Biosensor 1AX	Wireless medical biosensors and a COVID-19 Personal Symptom Monitoring App

HRCOFFEE	Digital workplace that connects all employees of a company with a bottom-up, smart and dynamic approach. It focuses on employee actions that translate into useful insights for management and strategic business development
cidaas	Cloud identity and access management
Precise COVID-19	Remote patients monitoring and clinical decision support for healthcare providers with COVID-19 patients
Walkie	It enables quick communication with co-workers via real time voice chat and allows for leaving messages across different applications
plazz AG Mobile Employee App	The plazz AG Mobile Employee App targets the digitalization of internal communication among the employer and its employees

A total of 22 different types of applications and tools have been analysed. The distribution per domain is represented in Figure 5, with the majority of applications and tools for Domain 1: Policy for older workers, especially in the COVID-19 case, with those focusing on interpersonal communication and Domain 2: Increasing job retention learning. As expected, this is a direct consequence of the importance of improving communication and adopting new skills that facilitate the work in the new post-COVID working environment.

Figure 5 Distribution of applications and tools per domain i.e., Domain 1: Policy for older workers, Domain 2 Increasing job retention, Domain 3 Improving productivity and workability, Domain 4: Healthy habits, Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms.

These domains distribution is also justified and verified by the analysed apps and technologies distribution per use cases, with a clear majority of applications found in those uses cases related with the new situation that we are living due to COVID-19. Strong emphasis is given to tools and applications related to facilitate the remotely continuous learning, UC5: Knowledge exchange platform and intergenerational collaboration

support, and skills acquisition, UC6 Productivity enhancement tools. The graphical distribution of tools is represented per pilot site in the Figure 6 Distribution of applications and tools per UCs .

Figure 6 Distribution of applications and tools per UCs UC1 Checklist platform, UC2 Participatory work orchestration, UC3 Support for musculoskeletal problem, UC4 Supporting health and well-being virtual coach, UC5: Knowledge exchange platform and intergenerational collaboration support, UC6: Productivity enhancement tool, UC7: Emergency/Panic button

Finally, detailed information about these applications and tools are included in Table 7.

Table 7 Selected applications and tools mapping with Ageing@work specific domains and pilot use cases:

	Problems addressed	Domain	UCs	Relevant comments for Ageing@Work
Comfy / SafeWorkspace	Workability	Domain 1 Domain 2 Domain 3	UC6	Only available for offices and setup is needed to configure each office room / building in accordance with COVID-19 regulations
BlogIn	Workability	Domain 1	UC2	Boosts collaboration and improves internal communication. Makes workplace feeling more friendly to the employees increases productivity. Encourages people to speak up
Muscle & Motion	Learning, cognitive functions Physical ability Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems)	Domain 3 Domain 4	UC3 UC4 UC6	In general, exercises should be done at home because the person should be focused on it and prepared (appropriate clothing).
Diet&Training by Ann	Physical ability Psychology/Mental abilities	Domain 3 Domain 4	UC4 UC3	
Neuropil	Transversal	Domain 5	UC2 UC6	
PIPEFORCE	Learning and cognitive functions	Domain 1 Domain 5	UC6 UC2 UC5	It is fully cloud-native (microservices, independent from any IaaS provider) and therefore unlimited scalable
Smartfence	Learning, cognitive functions	Domain 2	UC5	
SmartWe	Learning, cognitive functions Psychology/Mental abilities	Domain 1	UC5	
Spatial	Workability	Domain 1 Domain 5	UC5	
TrackLean	Learning cognitive functions	Domain 1	UC6	
Valarea	Learning cognitive functions	Domain 2	UC6 UC5	
LabsLand	Learning cognitive functions	Domain 2	UC6 UC5	Support pilots in terms of facilitating teleworking with those activities that only can be done in working environments
VIDSigner	Physical ability	Domain 3	UC6	Potentially, it could protect physical health while also improving efficiency

	Problems addressed	Domain	UCs	Relevant comments for Ageing@Work
Files.fm	Transversal	Domain 1	UC5	
OpenClassrooms	Learning cognitive functions	Domain 2	UC5	OpenClassrooms offers 1000+ courses focusing on in-demand skills and ranging from entrepreneurship, digital marketing to web development
Jobs@Skills	Learning cognitive functions	Domain 2	UC5	Develop workers skills thanks to the training courses developed by different partners universities, higher education institutions, training centres & companies.
LifeSignals Biosensor 1AX	Physical ability	Domain 1 Domain 4 Domain 5	UC3 UC4	The app shows and tracks the vital signs in real-time, using easy to follow traffic light charts
HRCOFFEE	Learning cognitive functions	Domain 2 Domain 3	UC2	
cidaas	Transversal	Transversal	Transversal	Optional Integration into existing AD/LDAP systems.
Precise COVID-19	Physical ability	Domain 4	UC4	
Walkie	Learning cognitive functions Psychology/Mental abilities	Domain 1 Domain 2 Domain 5	UC5 UC6	This is useful for faster communication, decision-making, having fewer meetings and understanding the voice tone of the sender of the message better which improves mutual understanding
plazz AG Mobile Employee App	Learning, cognitive functions Psychology/Mental abilities	Domain 1 Domain 2	UC6 UC5	The app can also be used as a Multi-Experience-App, where multiple use cases can be addressed in different designs via a content management system. Every instance can be customized individually. Data on app usage can be exported and downloaded. Using the Matomo tool (https://matomo.org/)

3.1.4 Overall results on benchmarking of applications and tools

A total of 48 applications and tools used in current working environments have been analysed in the T2.1. Just to summarize the work done in D2.2 and D2.7 following figures represent the domains and use cases covered by the total of applications and tools analysed in both deliverables. For more information about the applications and tools not included in this document, refer to D2.2 Supporting motivating and persuasive approaches tools and metrics, v1 section 3.1 Applications and tools.

Figure 11 presents the final results of the best practices included in the benchmarking done in the corresponding task. The domain more frequently address is Domain 4.

Figure 7 Total number of applications and tools (D2.1 and D2.7) included in the benchmarking addressed domains i.e., Domain 1: Policy for older workers, Domain 2 Increasing job retention, Domain 3 Improving productivity and workability, Domain 4: Healthy habits, Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms.

Therefore, the following figure represents the use cases most affected by these best practices, taking into account the results of both deliverables. In this case, UC3: Support musculoskeletal problem is revealed to benefit mostly from the proposed best practices.

Figure 8 Use Cases distribution of the Applications and tools analyzed in D2.1 and D2.7 UC1 Checklist platform, UC2 Participatory work orchestration, UC3 Support for musculoskeletal problem, UC4 Supporting health and well-being virtual coach, UC5: Knowledge exchange platform and intergenerational collaboration support, UC6: Productivity enhancement tool, UC7: Emergency/Panic button

3.2 Best practices

In this section, best practices to increase the workability are analysed, with the inclusion of 14 additional best practices, all of them proposed in the last 5 years. From them, 5 are specifically focused on the COVID-19, all of them for specifically addressing issue that concern aged workers. The issues to deal with them as risky group are both to support the back-to-work in safety conditions and the transition to new workflows and work understanding. Similarly to the practices proposed in the previous version of this deliverable, **Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.** includes the general description of each of the best practices and a summary of their benefits for Ageing@work purposes. They are linked as well with main domains and use cases addressed by the project. Finally, some graphs classify the best practices analysed per UCs and per domain of use. References of the included best practices are in Annexes section. The COVID-19 specific best practices are highlighted in the table with grey background.

Table 8 Best practices

Name	Summary
COVID-19 and its implications for research on workability	Description of the effects of COVID-19 in the understanding of the workability concept, in terms of its antecedents (job demands, job resources) and outcomes (job satisfaction, performance, motivation, strain and exit intentions and behaviours) and offers research directions to better capture the COVID-19 experiences of older workers in the theoretical aspects of workability.
Opening the Workplace After COVID-19: What Lessons Can be Learned	This best practice focuses on the COVID-19 workplace reopening process and underlines its special difficulties – such as extraordinary rules pertaining to physical distancing, personal protective equipment,

from Return-to-Work Research?	and physical guards, the efficacy of which is still unknown – and how workers adapt and function under these circumstances, including older workers, who are among those most susceptible to virus-related risks.
For Whom the Pandemic Tolls A Person-Centric Analysis of Older Workers	Brief description of three broad characteristics of pandemics: mortality salience, isolation from the workplace, and rising unemployment
Normalization Process Theory (NPT)	Theory that could be applied in examining organizational readiness for tech-driven work practices and new work configurations rapidly emerging in COVID-19 pandemic.
Bulpros – COVID-19 response	Consultation and support in implementing new remote working practices, consultation on how to adapt business to the fast changing situation, as well as with the implementation of the best solutions.
Design of digital coaches for health and wellness in the workplace	The design and methodology of sprint design and design thinking has been used for building and testing prototype. The prototype built has been a product-service system in physical pocket size product connected to an application, aimed at remote collaboration.
Work in the 21st Century: New Directions for Ageing and Adult Development	The authors analyse two frameworks of adult development over the past 3 decades, in a context characterized by changes in modern work experience brought about by the confluence of technology advancement, demographics (increasing number of adults who continue to work well into their 60s and 70s.), organizational practices (e.g., career success is no longer determined within a single organization, need of an agentic career orientation in later adulthood), and economic conditions, that interact with adult development to affect successful aging and longer working lives:
Digital Finance Competency Coach	Older employees and new ones can rate their competencies in respective responsible financial areas and receive suggested trainings
EHS training	Mandatory and voluntary EHS training opportunities for all employees and tailored to their respective function in the company.
Extended Work Life: A Growing Phenomenon	The author suggests that rather than watching mature workers go out the door or hastening their exit, organizational decision makers seeking to optimise productivity and profitability would be smart to institute policies and programs designed to maximize the talents of their mature workers.
Siemens One SRM	Online tool for purchasing goods and products including billing management
ZEOS	Online tool for booking vacation and managing sick leave
A systematic review of interventions to promote work participation in older workers	Systematic review to synthesize evidence on the effectiveness of interventions aimed at promoting work participation in older workers
Siemens locations are OHSAS 18001 zertifiziert	OHSAS 18001: Identify risks due to accidents or overload in good time and implement effective measures to protect your employees.
Time4You	Time4You enables employees to take additional days off and thus creates space and flexibility for individual time planning.

<p>Developing an Extended Model of the Relation between Work Motivation and Health as Affected by the Work Ability as Part of a Corporate Age Management Approach</p>	<p>It aims at developing an extended model of the relation between work motivation and health as affected by work ability and at deriving a host of measures that enterprises can apply as part of a corporate age management policy to counteract the impact of demographic changes.</p>
<p>Work in the 21st Century: New Directions for Aging and Adult Development</p>	<p>The authors analyse two frameworks of adult development over the past 3 decades: The adult intellect, with an identification of the domain knowledge and skills and the work motivation, conceptualized as the resource allocation perspective.</p>

A total of 13 different types of best practices have been analysed. The distribution per domain is represented in Figure 9, with the majority of best practices for Domain 2: Increasing job retention, Domain 5: Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms and Domain 1: Policy for older workers.

Figure 9 Distribution of best practices per domain i.e., Domain 1: Policy for older workers, Domain 2 Increasing job retention, Domain 3 Improving productivity and workability, Domain 4: Healthy habits, Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms.

Contrary to the results obtained in the previous deliverable, in this case, most of the practices are transversal to every of the domain, so the UCs are practically obtained the same results. We can highlight in this case, UC6: Productivity enhancement tools and UC2: Participatory work orchestration, but physical status and well-being (UC4 and UC3), because most of the practices related to COVID-19 are focused on the participation of workers, productivity and better management of the situations, that could be a change of paradigm in the ageing and workability research. The graphical distribution of best practices is represented per pilot site in the figure 8.

Figure 10 Distribution of best practices per UCs UC1 Checklist platform, UC2 Participatory work orchestration, UC3 Support for musculoskeletal problem, UC4 Supporting health and well-being virtual coach, UC5: Knowledge exchange platform and intergenerational collaboration support, UC6: Productivity enhancement tool, UC7: Emergency/Panic button

Finally, detailed information about these best practices is included in Table 9.

Table 9 Selected best practices mapping with Ageing@work specific domains and pilot use cases:

	Problems addressed	Domain	UCs	Relevant comments for Ageing@Work
COVID-19 and its implications for research on workability	Workability	Domain 5 Domain 2	Transversal	Safety implications of the new normal situation should be considered in the Ageing@Work project. The use of the teleworking as a demonstration of successful transition to better balance between private life and work, with the necessary strategies to do this transition as better as possible.
Opening the Workplace After COVID-19: What Lessons Can be Learned from Return-to-Work Research?	Psychology and mental ability Workability	Domain 1 Domain 4 Domain 5	Transversal	Some of the best practice results can be added as additional requirements for management tools of virtual coach, such as the impact of physical distancing monitoring, rescheduled elements of production, or reminders about the new safety measures
For Whom the Pandemic Tolls A Person-Centric Analysis of Older Workers	Learning, cognitive functions Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) Workability	Transversal	Transversal	Evaluation of the impact of COVID19 with the Siemens pre-pilot could contribute to the SOA of this practice
Normalization Process Theory (NPT)	Workability	Domain 5	Transversal	Implications of the theory could be addressed in the evaluation process of the solution
Bulpros – COVID-19 response	Learning, cognitive functions	Domain 2 Domain 5	UC5 UC6	Solutions in the ANEFA pilot could not be applicable and siemens seems to be workability solutions already deployed
Design of digital coaches for health and wellness in the workplace	Physical ability Psychology/Mental abilities Workability	Domain 4	UC4	The solution could be useful to improve usability and navigation using the worker tools, especially the virtual coach

	Problems addressed	Domain	UCs	Relevant comments for Ageing@Work
Work in the 21st Century: New Directions for Aging and Adult Development	Learning, cognitive functions Physical ability Sensory ability Psychology/Mental abilities Workability	Domain 1 Domain 2 Domain 3 Domain 4	Transversal	The main benefit of this best practice is to contribute to the understanding of ageing and adult development in the context of the changing nature of work, employment, and workforce development, by proposing six relevant themes to be considered. It shows that modern approaches to adult intellectual and motivational development provide the scientific foundations for changing organizational practices that have contributed to the use of persistent, but erroneous older worker stereotypes.
Digital Finance Competency Coach	Learning, cognitive functions Workability	Domain 2 Domain 3	UC2 UC5	Study the possibility to include specific content of this solution in the project
EHS training	Sensory ability Physical ability	Domain 2 Domain 3 Domain 4	UC2 UC6	Safety and health as well as environmental protection benefit everyone and depending on the position in the company training periods range from weekly to yearly. Additional trainings and materials are available online at any time. Analyze if they can be added to the A@W platform
Extended Work Life: A Growing Phenomenon	Transversal	Domain 1 Domain 2	Transversal	Include as part of the validation issues
Siemens One SRM	Workability	Domain 2 Domain 3	UC6	
ZEOS	Workability	Domain 1 Domain 2 Domain 3	UC6 UC2	
A systematic review of interventions to promote work participation in older workers	Workability	Transversal	Transversal	There was moderate evidence that work participation was improved by multi-component interventions encompassing at least two of three components (health service delivery, coordination of services, and work modifications).

	Problems addressed	Domain	UCs	Relevant comments for Ageing@Work
Additional Leave as the Determinant of Retirement Timing— Retaining Older Workers in Norway	Physical ability Psychology/Mental abilities	Domain 2	UC2	Additional Leave? adds to the pros for continuing working, motivating the choice of later exit over early retirement against other factors “pulling” or “pushing” older workers out of work
Older Worker Identity and Job Performance: The Moderator Role of Subjective Age and Self-Efficacy	Psychology/Mental abilities	Domain 1 Domain 2	Transversal	The study has been conducted with reference to the Spanish context and findings may not be transferable to other cultural environments due to the existence of cultural differences.
The Employability of Older Workers as Teleworkers: An Appraisal of Issues and an Empirical Study	Physical ability Psychology/Mental abilities Workability	Domain 1 Domain 5	Transversal	The research is agnostic with respect to the industry sectors (study sample included 314 managers from a large variety of companies in the United States).

	Problems addressed	Domain	UCs	Relevant comments for Ageing@Work
Current and future industrial changes: Demographic change and measures for elderly workers in industry 4.0	Learning, cognitive functions Physical ability Workability	Domain 1 Domain 2 Domain 5	UC3 UC4	Describe the results of the application of the best practice in the described environment. Include the number of involved people, and indicators of improvement in the workability (example, Index WAI)
Universal design frameworks for policies in the workplace: Case studies and best practices	Workability	Domain 5	UC3 UC4 UC6	
Lessons learned from the Kronos research project	Psychology/Mental abilities	Domain 2 Domain 3	UC2 UC4	Suitable working time models are one important measure to maintain or even improve the working duration? of older workers.
Siemens locations are OHSAS 18001 zertifiziert	Workability	Transversal	UC3 UC4	Specific Siemens standards
Time4You	Workability	Domain 2 Domain 3	UC2 UC3 UC4	

<p>Developing an Extended Model of the Relation between Work Motivation and Health as Affected by the Work Ability as Part of a Corporate Age Management Approach</p>	<p>Psychology/Mental abilities Workability</p>	<p>Domain 5</p>	<p>UC4 UC6</p>	
<p>Work in the 21st Century: New Directions for Aging and Adult Development</p>	<p>Transversal</p>	<p>Transversal</p>	<p>Transversal</p>	

3.3 Overall results on benchmarking of best practices

At last, a total of 27 best practices related to the ageing process in working environment have been analysed in the T2.1. Just to summary the work done in D2.2 and D2.7 following figures represent the domains and use case covered by the total of the best practices analysed in both deliverables. For more information about the best practices not included in this document, refer to D2.2 Supporting motivating and persuasive approaches tools and metrics, v1 section 3.2 Best Practices.

Figure 11 presents the final results of the best practices included in the benchmarking done in the corresponding task. The domain more frequently addressed is Domain 5: Workability, very close to the Domain 2, 3, 4. Domain less addressed is the Domain 1: Policy for older works, which, as mentioned in section **Error! Reference source not found.**, could be justified by the difficulties to involve decision makers in the process of addressing aging problem at work.

Figure 11 Total number of Best Practices (D2.1 and D2.7) included in the benchmarking addressed domains i.e., Domain 1: Policy for older workers, Domain 2 Increasing job retention, Domain 3 Improving productivity and workability, Domain 4: Healthy habits, Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms.

As well following figure represents the use cases most affected by these best practices, taking into account the results of both deliverables. In this case, UC4: Supporting health and well-being virtual coach and UC2: Participatory work orchestration are the most suitable to benefit from the proposed best practices.

Figure 12 Use Cases distribution of the best practices analyzed in D2.1 and D2.7 UC1 Checklist platform, UC2 Participatory work orchestration, UC3 Support for musculoskeletal problem, UC4 Supporting health and well-being virtual coach, UC5: Knowledge exchange platform and intergenerational collaboration support, UC6: Productivity enhancement tool, UC7: Emergency/Panic button

4. Overall conclusions of benchmarking

COVID-19 has changed the way people work and the modifications will continue in the future with direct implication on workability. Among workforce, aged workers are one of the more directly affected groups, since they are more susceptible to the virus. Traditionally, an increase in age has been associated with a decrease on workability. The association between health and workability can impact negatively an aged worker, but in a COVID-19 situation, where the workers should take additional measurement to do their jobs in safety conditions, companies, workers, and governments should be concerned about the implication on their ability to work safely. The greater sense of control at work in term of scheduling, physical environment, or flexibility, derivate from this pandemic situation, can on contrary, have a benefit to the aged workers' workability.

In this sense, current updates on the benchmarking of supporting motivational tools and metrics have shown the importance of technology on adapting working environments, and in some way, the virus has boosted the uptake of new technologies in most of the working environments. We can highlight here the enormous number of new applications oriented to improve communication between partners, an evidence of the importance of intergenerational relationships at work. These tools are key in the process and can break the barriers of ageing stereotypes down.

Another important area that was found in those practices, tools and technologies, aimed to provide long-term learning approaches, that means, adaptation to changing environments. That could be a good point to address, since we know from previous economic recession, that individuals who are closer to retirement usually are not the preference group to hire and train. The use of new technologies such as eLearning or VR can make more attractive the intergenerational training, open new opportunities for retraining older individuals and address the need or wish, to work for longer.

All of this is represented on the change in the distribution of the domains addressed by best practices, technologies and applications. While in the first version of this deliverable the role of the management has higher importance (i.e. domain 1, domain 2 and domain 5), in this case, domain 3 is more related to the improvement of the individual conditions of the workers, acquired importance, together with domain 2, in those practices oriented to long-term workability and worker retainment. Work life balance has also acquired importance in this second state of the art analysis. This approach is more similar to the Ageing@Work one, and those solutions and best practices in the field should be taken into account in order to improve the final evidence of the project.

Evaluation protocol should take into account several of the approaches offered by the solutions analysed especially those related to the best practices, in order to check if Ageing@Work system is compliant with those practices.

References

LIVE LONGER, WORK LONGER. (2006). OECD. doi:ISBN-92-64-035877

Leonardo, R. (2018). PICO: Model for Clinical Questions. *Evid Based Med Pract*, 3(115), 2.

Feißel, A. P. (2018). Developing an Extended Model of the Relation between Work Motivation and Health as Affected by the Work Ability as Part of a Corporate Age Management Approach. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 15(4), 779.

Knauth P., K. D. (2013). Development and Evaluation of Working-Time Models for the Ageing Workforce: Lessons Learned from the KRONOS Research Project. . En F. E. Schlick C. (Ed.), *Age-Differentiated Work Systems*. (págs. 45-63). Berlin, Heidelberg.: Springer,.

Wolf, M. K. (2018). CURRENT AND FUTURE INDUSTRIAL CHALLENGES: DEMOGRAPHIC CHANGE AND MEASURES FOR ELDERLY WORKERS IN INDUSTRY 4.0. *Annals of the Faculty of Engineering Hunedoara-international journal of engineering,, 1*, 16.

Kern, C. (2018). Universal Design Frameworks for Policies in the Workplace: Case Studies and Best Practices (Doctoral dissertation. State University of New York at Buffalo.

Hermansen, Å. (2016). Additional leave as the determinant of retirement timing—retaining older workers in Norway. *Retaining Older Workers, , 4*(4).

Hermansen, Å. (2015). Retaining older workers: The effect of phased retirement on delaying early retirement. *Nordic Journal of Social Research*, 6.

Rodríguez-Cifuentes, F., Farfán, J., & Topa, G. (2018). Older Worker Identity and Job Performance: The Moderator Role of Subjective Age and Self-Efficacy. I, 15(12), 2731. (s.f.). *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 15(12), 2731.

Sharit, J. C. (2009). The employability of older workers as teleworkers: An appraisal of issues and an empirical study. *Human Factors and Ergonomics in Manufacturing & Service Industries*, 19(5), 457-477.

Arndt, A. A. (2017, July). Guideline for the implementation of human-oriented assistance systems in smart factories. *International Conference on Applied Human Factors and Ergonomics*. Springer, Cham.

Dordoni, P. (2017). AGING AT WORK: The moderating role of age in occupational wellbeing . Doctoral dissertation, Dissertation Thesis, Pavia (IT): University of Pavia.

McLinton, S. M. (2018). Psychosocial factors impacting workplace injury rehabilitation: Evaluation of a concise screening tool. *Journal of occupational rehabilitation*, 28(1), 121-129.

Andersen, P. A. (2018). Testing the long-term effects of the Go Sun Smart worksite health communication campaign: A group-randomized experimental study. . *Journal of Communication*, 58(3), 447-471.

Lallemand, T. &. (2009). Are older workers harmful for firm productivity? *The Economist*, 15(3), 273-292.

Versluis, A. V. (2018). Effectiveness of a smartphone-based worry-reduction training for stress reduction: A randomized-controlled trial. *Psychology & health*, 33(9), 1079-1099.

Annex I: Best practices analysed.

This annex presents the best practices and research on workability factors and barriers for elderly workers. In particular, we present several researches related to the COVID-19 implications since they have revolted the workability in terms of routines and also implication of the illness for aged workers.

Name of the best practice	COVID-19 and its implications for research on workability
Short description	The paper discusses the effects of COVID-19 in the understanding of the workability concept, in terms of its antecedents (job demands, job resources) and outcomes (job satisfaction, performance, motivation, strain and exit intentions and behaviours) and offers research directions to better capture the COVID-19 experiences of older workers in the theoretical aspects of workability.
Covered area/industrial sector	All sectors
Promoter	Corresponding author: Donald M. Truxillo, Kemmy Business School, University of Limerick, Castletroy, Limerick, Ireland, V94 PH93, Donald.Truxillo@ul.ie
Indicative cost	Not applicable
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Workability The effects of COVID-19 crisis to workability are discussed.
Domain/type of solution	<u>Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms</u> To adapt work environment to ageing functional decline To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	Not applicable

<p>Results and benefits of the best practice</p>	<p>It is important to understand the societal and organizational influences on workability, as different organizational and societal policy contexts could influence one’s perception of meeting work demands safely.</p> <p>Empirical research is needed to better understand how a number of individual differences, such as risk tolerance and COVID-19 concerns, might affect workability.</p> <p>Health-focused measures of workability might be particularly affected as based on assessing employee’s underlying health conditions.</p> <p>COVID-19 affects decisions to retire among older workers.</p> <p>Research is needed to understand how COVID-19 concerns, economic concerns and workability may impact on older workers’ wellbeing and presenteeism.</p> <p>Research is needed to understand how COVID-19 influences workability in the return-to-work phase.</p> <p>Research is needed to examine whether workability is permanently affected by shocks such as a pandemic, even after the threat has passed.</p>
<p>Applicability limitations</p>	<p>Not applicable directly due to the restrictions of the project duration</p>

Name of the best practice	Opening the Workplace After COVID-19: What Lessons Can be Learned from Return-to-Work Research?
Short description	This best practice focuses on the COVID-19 workplace reopening process and underlines its special difficulties – such as extraordinary rules pertaining to physical distancing, personal protective equipment, and physical guards, the efficacy of which is still unknown – and how workers adapt and function under these circumstances, including older workers, who are among those most susceptible to virus-related risks.
Covered area/industrial sector	The authors do not address specific areas or industry sectors but state that occupational health and safety guidelines for reopening the workplace should be industry- or occupation-specific and consider the unique physical, psychological, and social workplace factors of different work settings.
Promoter	William S. Shaw, wshaw@uchc.edu , University of Connecticut School of Medicine, 263, Farmington Ave, Farmington, CT 06030, USA
Indicative cost	There is no cost associated to this best practice.
Problem addressed (explain specifically how it is addressed)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opening of workplaces during COVID-19 is occurring against a backdrop of heightened levels of psychological distress in the community that crosses all sociodemographic divides. • Returning to an uncertain working environment presents an additional stressor that can further affect the mental health of workers. <input type="checkbox"/> Workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workers who experience COVID-19 symptoms and return to work after a period of illness and quarantine may experience fatigue, anxiety, and/or reduced work tolerance. • It is unclear how conjoint work that necessitates close physical proximity will be managed, as it seems that mandatory physical distancing will be a condition for workplace opening. • Domestic pressure arising from the health or risk of ill-health in families can have a significant effect on workers' wellbeing, sleep, and mental health, with possible increases in presenteeism and work absence.
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 1: Policy for older workers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers. • Domain 4 Healthy habits programs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leisure and sleep educational programs. • Vacuums and medical check (early prevention programs) • Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To adapt the work environment to ageing functional decline

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To adapt the work environment to chronic illness or diseases
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	No training issues are reported by the authors.
Results and benefits of the best practice	<p>The best practice results in several recommendations for companies reopening work after Covid-19:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In providing support and guidance, managers will be asked to address a wide range of effects not only of the virus, but of the impact of physical distancing as well. This is particularly important if they are required to monitor and enforce new working arrangements. Workplace flexibility and modification will be needed to support safe workplace openings, and this will vary substantially among industry and occupation. Changes in social interaction will require that many standard practices within employing organizations would be re-evaluated and revised. Just like in return-to-work after injury, employers may struggle to maintain uniform and fair practices while also being responsive to the concerns of individual workers, and it will be important to involve multiple stakeholders in this process. Workplace openings should prioritize the needs of disadvantaged workers, as they are most likely to have higher environmental exposures and inflexible job tasks, and they will be most threatened by job loss and unemployment.
Applicability limitations	No specific limitations are reported by the authors

Name of the best practice	For Whom the Pandemic Tolls A Person-Centric Analysis of Older Workers
Short description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • worker-centric perspective on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic for the aging workforce • brief description of three broad characteristics of pandemics: mortality salience, isolation from the workplace, and rising unemployment
Covered area/industrial sector	i.a. comparison of low-wage and high-wage work
Promoter	Ruth Kanfer School of Psychology 654 Cherry St., MC 0170 Georgia Institute of Technology Atlanta, GA 30332-0170 E-mail: rkanfer@gatech.edu
Indicative cost	no information
Problem addressed (explain specifically how it is addressed)	X Learning, cognitive functions X Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) X Workability mortality salience, isolation from the workplace, and rising unemployment
Domain/type of solution	No solutions in the actual sense are presented. Rather, the need for research on the impact of the pandemic on the ability of older workers to work is presented.
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	No information
Results and benefits of the	Research is needed to fill large gaps in our knowledge about how pandemics affect older adult need profiles, including how increased mortality salience changes attitudes and behaviours, how changes in one's workplace affects feelings of social isolation and work motivation, and who chooses unplanned, forced retirement.
Applicability limitations	No information

General information	Best Practice on motivational approaches
Name of the best practice	<p>Normalization Process Theory (NPT) (Carroll, N., & Conboy, K. (2020). Normalising the “new normal”: Changing tech-driven work practices under pandemic time pressure. <i>International Journal of Information Management</i>, 55, 102186.)</p>
Short description	<p>Theory that could be applied in examining organisational readiness for tech-driven work practices and new work configurations rapidly emerging in COVID-19 pandemic.</p> <p>The COVID-19 pandemic has had massive implications for the nature of work and the role that technology plays in the workplace. Organisations have been forced into rapid ‘big bang’ introduction of technology and ‘tech-driven’ practices in an unprecedented and time-pressured manner. In many cases there has been little training or reflection on how the practices and associated technology should be introduced and integrated or adapted to suit the new workplace context.</p> <p>The authors argue that there is a need for a more reflexive ‘normalisation’ of work practices and the role technology plays. The paper draws on Normalisation Process Theory (NPT) and its underlying components of cohesion, cognitive participation, collective action and reflexive monitoring. Authors focus on the changing nature of work and adoption of remote working practices. The paper uses NPT to examine current thinking and approaches and offer some guidelines to inform research and practice.</p> <p>NPT has clear applicability to pandemics to examine the normalisation of a new tech-driven work practice through the following theoretical constructs:</p> <p>Cohesion - refers to the process of sensemaking that individuals and organisations undergo in order to promote or inhibit the routine embedding of a practice. For example, this allows to define and examine the implications of decisions on defining and (re)organising a practice to accommodate technology-driven change to work practices during pandemics.</p> <p>Cognitive participation - examines how stakeholders engage in the newly adopted practice. This allows us to identify the social and technical roles and responsibilities which are developed to sustain and participate in technology-driven change to work practices in response to pandemics.</p> <p>Collective action - focuses on the work that individuals and teams have to do to change practice by enacting the new practice. This allows us to examine the specific practices, organising factors, and tools used to enact and sustain new practices facilitated by teams working towards the same vision of technology-driven work practices.</p> <p>Reflexive monitoring - describes the value realisation inherent in the informal and formal appraisal of new technology-driven work practices and the reported process improvements. These can also provide new insights on the impact of pandemics on forging new organising structures, social norms, group processes and conventions as a result of new technology-driven work practices.</p>

Covered area/industrial sector	Any sector where remote working using ICT is included
Promoter	Contact info: National University of Ireland Galway Noel Carroll noel.carroll@nuigalway.ie
Indicative cost	No costs
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Workability
Domain/type of solution	Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms To adapt work environment to aging functional decline To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases Adaptation to new work organization, new technologies, remote work
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	Training for organization is needed to implement NPT.
Results and benefits of the solution	NPT can be used to better plan for changes in terms of organizational readiness to adopt new tech-driven practices or as an evaluation framework to assess changed organisational environments. Under the 16 NPT components, organisations can pinpoint organisational readiness for change and the value stakeholders place on the change, for example, growing task demands, resource availability, technostress and situational factors. NPT can be applied to identify and assess the new dimensions of technology-driven work practices and new work configurations. Such insights can guide practitioners on how to better manage group processes and conventions to identify how a practice is produced and modified to shape human behavioral patterns through technology-driven work practices. It is a theoretical approach and no evidence is available in context of COVID-19 pandemic.
Applicability limitations	-

Name of the application or technology	Bulpros – COVID-19 response
Short description	<p>Consultation and support in implementing new remote working practices, consultation on how to adapt business to the fast-changing situation, as well as with the implementation of the best solutions.</p> <p>Four main areas:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Supporting remote work through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Orientation session to cover the most critical aspects of adopting emergency remote work. Digital workspace emergency provisioning, covering tenant configuration, configuring security, core services and user onboarding. Managed Infrastructure – hosting files and applications on a secure, private and enterprise-grade infrastructure and taking care of IT operations. Training, guidance and best practices 2. Online security (email protection, endpoint protection, security awareness training) 3. Online customer service support and consultation (tool for customer service via video call, building-up virtual assistant, building-up virtual doctor) 4. Transitioning in-person events to virtual events <p>It is described as a COVID-19 response but it is a package of tools and consultancy on a remote work (not only in COVID-19 times).</p>
Covered area/industrial sector	Every industry implementing remote work digital tools
Manufacturer/provider	<p>Bulpros https://bulpros.tech/covid-19-response/ Bulgaria, Sofia, 1766 Business Park Sofia, bldg. 15A, fl.5, T: +359 889584032 F: +359 2 489 5883 Contact person: Radoslav Bratanov</p>
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	Not available
Licence	Bulpros
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions – it helps employees to learn to work remotely
Domain/type of solution	<p>Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) Learning and training tools and technologies Domain 5: Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms To adapt work environment to aging functional decline To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases</p>
Need of training to use the solution	The package contains training of employees

Results and benefits	Not available
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	For employees working remotely
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Name of the best practice	Design of digital coaches for health and wellness in the workplace
Short description	<p>The study explores how the design can play a fundamental role in bringing digital coaches and tangible interfaces aimed in active ageing in the workplace and in helping people stay healthy for longer to a final form that can be felt and perceived as useful by the users. The design and methodology of sprint design and design thinking has been used for building and testing prototype.</p> <p>The prototype built has been a product-service system in physical pocket size product connected to an application, aimed at remote collaboration.</p>
Covered area/industrial sector	
Promoter	Alessandra Rinaldi, Kiana Kianfar, alessandra.rinaldi@unifi.it ; kiana.kianfar@unifi.it
Indicative cost	Not available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical ability This APP is able to calculate time necessary to have a break and to drink water during working hours, reminding the user through notifications (visual and sound feedback)</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) The product-service includes an APP, which allows you to insert tasks and the time is available for each of them, based on the Gantt chart. All the members directly or indirectly involved in the project can have an overview of the scheduled tasks and are informed of their deadline</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Workability Each user is assigned a color at the time of registration on the APP and during any conversation by the device everyone is recognized by their color. The user can communicate with the team visually and vocally though the device</p>
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Domain 4 Healthy habits programs</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrition • Physical activity • Leisure and sleep educational programs • Vacuums and medical check (early prevention programs)
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	Not applicable
Results and benefits of the solution	<p>The tasks of a project can be visualized in every work phase, enhancing clarity, communication, motivation and time management and flexibility.</p> <p>The device provides the belonging sense to the work team through a tangible interface which creates a colorful avatar for each member of the group and keeps them participating during the work hours.</p>
Applicability limitations	

Name of the best practice	Work in the 21st Century: New Directions for Aging and Adult Development
Short description	<p>The authors analyse two frameworks of adult development over the past 3 decades, in a context characterized by changes in modern work experience brought about by the confluence of technology advancement, demographics (increasing number of adults who continue to work well into their 60s and 70s.), organizational practices (e.g., career success is no longer determined within a single organization, need of an agentic career orientation in later adulthood), and economic conditions, that interact with adult development to affect successful aging and longer working lives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The first framework focuses on adult intellect. It identifies domain knowledge and skills as a primary reflection of adult intelligence and considers the acquisition and maintenance of specialized knowledge. This perspective has three important implications for rethinking adult development: (1) Adult intelligence is more than an IQ score, as breadth and depth of domain knowledge also play a crucial role; (2) Domain knowledge and skills develop across the life span, well into middle-age and beyond; (3) Domain knowledge is determined in part by personality and interests, as they show important facilitative or impeding effects on the direction and intensity of effort allocated to acquiring and maintaining it • The second framework focuses on work motivation. It conceptualizes work motivation from an expectancy-based, resource allocation perspective, that posits individuals devote personal resources (e.g., effort) to a task or job based on their perceptions of three component functions that change in form across the life span: the effort-utility function, the perceived effort performance function, and the performance-utility function. Also important is the distinction between motivation “at work,” (e.g., high levels of task knowledge and experience among older workers may promote work motivation on tasks that younger (less experienced) workers view as largely unattainable without formidable effort) “to work,” (e.g., for most older workers, motivation to work involves some combination of perceived necessity and choice) and “to retire” (shift away from a work/no work decision, toward a process characterized by leaving one’s current job for activities ranging from full, but temporary workforce withdrawal to self-employed independent contractor to taking a job better suited to one’s interests or desire for work–family balance). <p>As a result of the analysis, six themes are proposed as guides for forging new directions in the world of 21st century work:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Move Toward a Scientific Account of Work Experience, Expertise, and Aging (rejecting the simplistic view that that older workers possess work experience and expertise, but that such knowledge and skills are either outdated or noncritical to modern job performance)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build More Relevant Adult Knowledge and Skill Assessments (e.g., assessments need to be developed to evaluate abilities such as efficacy of information retrieval (using technological aids), critical thinking, oral comprehension, and writing skills rather than just fluid abilities and “historical” crystallized abilities) • Conduct Regular Whole-Person Assessments (notion of whole-person monitoring of work-related attributes, e.g., knowledge, skills, abilities interests, attitudes, motivation) • Leverage Existing Knowledge and Skills for New Learning (e.g., learning among older workers is enhanced by utilizing motivating formats – e.g., self-paced – and existing knowledge structures) • Make a Place for All in the Knowledge Economy (emerging evidence suggests people will experience longer working lives in the future, but with increasingly different working experiences and outcomes) • Rethink the Nature of Human Work and Nature? of Adult Development in a Technologically Advanced World (consideration of human skill in optimizing and innovating technology, through a balance of exploitation and exploration, and in finding appropriate resources to solve problems)
Covered area/industrial sector	The analysis is not specific to a determined area or industrial sector.
Promoter	Correspondence concerning the article should be addressed to Phillip L. Ackerman or Ruth Kanfer, School of Psychology, Georgia Institute of Technology, 654 Cherry Street, MC 0170, Atlanta, GA 30332-0170. E-mail: plackerman@gatech.edu or rkanfer@gatech.edu
Indicative cost	The analysis does not report about specific actions with related costs but it concentrates on the overall scenario for older workers in the 21 st century.
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This best practice recognizes the importance of intelligence, knowledge, and skills when assessing work performance of older workers and argues that dimensions such as knowledge and skills are developed well into middle-age and beyond, and can contribute to counterbalance age-related decreases in other dimensions. • The authors note that a more complete view of intelligence that gives credit to the breadth and depth of domain knowledge clearly shows that older workers typically have a more robust repertoire of knowledge and skills than was previously thought. • The authors also recognize that personality and interest traits show important facilitative or impeding effects on the direction and intensity of effort allocated to acquiring and maintaining specialized domain knowledge, that also complicate the

	<p>assessment of older worker performance, away from the simplistic view that it is necessarily decreasing.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Sensory ability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although the authors acknowledge the decrease in sensory ability of older workers, they note that during the course of the 20th century, technological advances reduced the physical (muscle) and sensory and perceptual demands in many jobs. • This trend is continuing in the 21st century, in which technology-driven changes have shifted the emphasis in human work across many occupations away from physical competencies and toward the development of specialized knowledge and skills. □ Physical ability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The above items, related to sensory ability, also refer to physical ability. • However, the authors acknowledge that certain specific types of work, where the physical effort component is predominant, might still put older worker at a disadvantage, irrespective of the other dimensions above mentioned, and particularly as regards motivation □ Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This best practice underlines the crucial aspect of motivation, when assessing older workers performance and desire to continue to work (motivation at work, to work and to retire) • The authors question the myth that general work motivation declines across the life span, as a solid body of evidence shows to the contrary and research suggests a more nuanced developmental process. • Specifically, age-related changes in cognitive and physical abilities, knowledge and skills, and changing motive strength jointly influence the resource allocation calculus and regulatory strategies that workers use to select and accomplish goals. □ Workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The authors mention workability in the frame of the need to create a “workplace for all” in the knowledge economy, with reference to the need for Work-centered programs that include, for example, job redesign and workplace changes that sustain workability in later life (e.g., providing physical aids such as carpeted shop floors to reduce joint damage) and organizational supports for new skill learning (e.g., paid tuition for graduate education in computer science)
<p>Domain/type of solution</p>	<p>The best practice does not address specific solutions or tools, but provides reflection and proposes new research approaches that can form the basis for the conception of relevant solution/tools in many domains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 1: Policy for older workers • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability • Domain 4 Healthy habits programs
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	<p>The authors recognize the importance of training to support older workers in the 21st century. In particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research is needed to systematically evaluate the impact of different informal, formal, and mixed adult learning methods currently in use (e.g., mentoring, experience-based [on-the-job] training, online training, group simulator training, etc.) on the development and use of new job-related knowledge and skills, particularly among older workers. • Organizations have come to recognize that they have a responsibility for “supporting [employees] through training and education that help develop new skills for a rapidly changing world”. • To develop older workers potential, organizations must move away from one-size-fits-all approaches that may be suboptimal for some workers and toward tailored, self-paced training methods that build on extant knowledge.
Results and benefits of the best practice	<p>The main benefit of this best practice is to contribute to the understanding of aging and adult development in the context of the changing nature of work, employment, and workforce development, by proposing six relevant themes to be considered. It shows that modern approaches to adult intellectual and motivational development provide the scientific foundations for changing organizational practices that have contributed to the use of persistent, but erroneous older worker stereotypes.</p>
Applicability limitations	<p>No specific applicability limitations are reported by the authors</p>

Name of the best practice	Digital Finance Competency Coach
Short description	Older employees and new ones can rate their competencies in respective responsible financial areas and receive suggested trainings
Covered area/industrial sector	Finance area
Promoter	Siemens
Indicative cost	Not available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions <input type="checkbox"/> Workability
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity programs tools • New therapies Yoga, Taichi, Mindfulness • Leisure programs
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	Available trainings need to be gathered and linked to skills needed including the level of proficiency
Results and benefits of the	Older employees and new ones can, when time is available, brush up on new issues and strengthen old ones. Every employee in finance or partially responsible for financial issues can get self- taught and get up to the latest knowledge.
Applicability limitations	Internal trainings or external training providers need to be present and inserted in the proper database.

Name of the best practice	EHS training
Short description	Mandatory and voluntary EHS training opportunities for all employees and tailored to their respective function in the company.
Covered area/industrial sector	All areas
Promoter	Siemens EHS and Learning Campus
Indicative cost	Not available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Sensory ability <input type="checkbox"/> Physical ability
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity programs tools • New therapies Yoga, Taichi, Mindfulness • Leisure programs • Domain 4 Healthy habits programs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrition • Physical activity • Leisure and sleep educational programs • Vacuums and medical check (early prevention programs)
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	Internal training materials need to be available or acquired from external providers. Everyone in the company from office to industry worker benefit and is self motivated to participate.
Results and benefits of the	Safety and health as well as environmental protection benefit everyone and depending on the function and position in the company training periods range from weekly to yearly. Additional trainings and materials are available online at any time.
Applicability limitations	Nearly no limitations – mandatory trainings need to be defined and participation has to be documented.

Name of the best practice	Extended Work Life: A Growing Phenomenon Fideler, E. F. (2020). Extended Work Life: A Growing Phenomenon. Public Policy & Aging Report, 30(3), 79-81.
Short description	<p>Longer lifespans have created the relatively new phenomenon of extended work life (EWL) and its implications for individuals, for-profit and non-profit organizations, government agencies, and society as a whole.</p> <p>ELS is not new. What is different today is the scale and scope of the EWL phenomenon. We should be recognizing that a growing but largely untapped natural resource—the record number of older adults who want to or need to extend their working life—is paired with the demand for policies and programs that will help employers to hire and retain them. On that basis, EWL looks to become the norm.</p> <p>The author suggests that rather than watching mature workers go out the door or hastening their exit, organizational decision makers seeking to optimise productivity and profitability would be smart to institute policies and programs designed to maximize the talents of their mature workers.</p> <p>In the meantime, Clark and Ritter’s (2019) survey, for example, found that only one option had been implemented by the majority of HR managers: financial well-being/retirement planning. Few companies were offering other options to support the EWL of their mature workers, such as reduced hours or responsibilities, part-time employment, a formal phased retirement program, additional training, or modified working conditions.</p> <p>Various solutions should be implemented in organisations in order to fight the age stereotypes and extend working life.</p>
Covered area/industrial sector	General
Promoter	Elizabeth F. Fideler, EdD Center on Aging and Work, Boston College, Chestnut Hill, Massachusetts E-mail: lizpaulfideler@gmail.com
Indicative cost	-
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions <input type="checkbox"/> Sensory ability <input type="checkbox"/> Physical ability <input type="checkbox"/> Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) <input type="checkbox"/> Workability All areas are addressed but not specifically. Author suggests various actions, in order to postpone retirement, that should be implemented in organisations.
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 1: Policy for older workers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers. • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies

Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	No
Results and benefits of the	In theory, extending retirement age should be achieved.
Applicability limitations	-

Name of the best practice	Siemens One SRM
Short description	Online tool for purchasing goods and products including billing management
Covered area/industrial sector	Office and industry supplies
Promoter	Siemens
Indicative cost	Not available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Workability
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity programs tools • New therapies Yoga, Taichi, Mindfulness • Leisure programs
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	Training is needed – online courses and webinars
Results and benefits of the	During the COVID-19 pandemic everyone in home office or on premises can order the necessary supplies
Applicability limitations	Need to be implemented and linked to SAP and external suppliers

Name of the best practice	ZEOS
Short description	Online tool for booking vacation and managing sick leave
Covered area/industrial sector	Available for all employees either in office or in work floor
Promoter	Siemens
Indicative cost	Not available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)) <input type="checkbox"/> Workability
Domain/type of solution	Domain 1: Policy for older workers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers. • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity programs tools • New therapies Yoga, Taichi, Mindfulness • Leisure programs
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	No training is needed and motivation is to simply manage vacation or sick leave without any through non- electronic communication
Results and benefits of the	Available for all employees worldwide either by computer or mobile app. Saves time and effort and reduces administrative issues.
Applicability limitations	Needs to be integrated in the HR environment and linked to SAP

Name of the best practice	A systematic review of interventions to promote work participation in older workers
Short description	Systematic review to synthesize evidence on the effectiveness of interventions aimed at promoting work participation in older workers
Covered area/industrial sector	No special area/industrial sector covered, general review
Promoter	Ivan Steenstra, Institute for Work & Health, Toronto, Ontario, Canada, isteenstra@morneaushepell.com
Indicative cost	No information possible
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	X Workability Evidence from 14 studies were synthesized in 4 different intervention categories: multi-component, exercise, medication and other interventions.
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 1: Policy for older workers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers. • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity programs tools • New therapies Yoga, Taichi, Mindfulness • Leisure programs • Domain 4 Healthy habits programs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrition • Physical activity • Leisure and sleep educational programs • Vaccines and medical check (early prevention programs) • Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To adapt work environment to aging functional decline • To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases <p>Evidence from 14 studies were synthesized in 4 different intervention categories: multi-component, exercise, medication and other interventions.</p>
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	No information possible
Results and benefits of the	There was moderate evidence that work participation was improved by multi-component interventions encompassing at least two of three components (health service delivery, coordination of services, and work modifications). These types of interventions could be considered for use in practice. There is not enough evidence to recommend exercise interventions, pharmaceutical interventions, different types of surgery,

	patient education or work accommodation alone to improve work participation.
Applicability limitations	No information possible

Annex II: Technologies analysed

Name of the application or technology	Applying Blockchain Technology to Address the Crisis of Trust during the COVID-19 Pandemic ¹
Short description	The widespread death and disruption caused by the COVID-19 pandemic has revealed deficiencies of existing institutions regarding the protection of human health and well-being. Both the lack of accurate and timely data and pervasive misinformation are causing increasing harm and growing tension between data privacy and public health concerns. Blockchain technology, with its distributed trust networks and cryptography-based security, may provide solutions to data-related trust problems.
Covered area/industrial sector	all industrial sectors
Manufacturer/provider	Author: Anjum Khurshid 1, MD, PhD, The University of Texas at Austin , Austin, TX, US Publication on JMIR Medical Informatics doi:10.2196/20477
Market availability	Yes, use of blockchain technology in health sector is still in its infancy
Indicative cost	
Licence	
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	X Physical ability blockchain technology may help to deal with the challenges faced by existing technologies to track medical supplies and infected patients during COVID-19 pandemic
Domain/type of solution	Domain 4 Healthy habits programs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrition • Physical activity • Leisure and sleep educational programs • Vacuums and medical check (early prevention programs)
Need of training to use the solution	Expert knowledge in the field of blockchain technology

¹ Despite the fact that this technology has not direct applicability on Ageing@Work, we have included here as example of the efforts of industry and service providers to adapt their working environments to the restrictions with innovative solutions. In this case the applicability of the blockchain technologies to the pandemic control and management.

Results and benefits	<p>“Blockchain is being applied in innovative ways that are relevant to the current COVID-19 crisis. For example blockchain technology may help to deal with the challenges faced by existing technologies to track medical supplies and infected patients. [...] Blockchain can be used to create “trustless” systems that can help resolve the tension between maintaining privacy and addressing public health needs in the fight against COVID-19. [...] Blockchain relies on a distributed, robust, secure, privacy-preserving, and immutable record framework that can positively transform the nature of trust, value sharing, and transactions. A nationally coordinated effort to explore blockchain to address the deficiencies of existing systems and a partnership of academia, researchers, business, and industry are suggested to expedite the adoption of blockchain in health care.” Anjum Khurshid</p>
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	
Interoperability with other solution	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners</p>

Name of the application or technology	IIM LEAD (Lean, Energy Efficient, Agile, Digital) Learning factory
Short description	<p>A learning factory is an isolated and reproducible environment to conduct research and trainings on different industrial related topics. The main purpose of a learning factory is teaching and/or training and/or research. In LEAD learning factory of Graz University of Technology, participants assemble a functional scooter in three set-up states for didactic reasons: initial state, optimized lean state and digital state. Participants work in the initial state where a customized scooter is assembled under poor ergonomic conditions. In the optimized state, also the ergonomic situation is changed in terms of cycle times, aggregation of work and avoidance of awkward body postures. Since 2016 many digital technologies such as augmented reality glasses, gesture and mimic control, digital work orders, process control with RFID, etc. have been introduced.</p> <p>Age-related changes to human working abilities are addressed as following in the IIM LEAD factory: a training for ergonomics and age-appropriate workplace design is currently developed. As a second contribution, the LEAD Factory is currently used as a research environment in the public funded research project “EnableMe50+” where technological and methodological assistance solutions for industry workers are researched based on a developed assessment method that points out age critical work tasks. Thirdly, the technologies already implemented and tested within the research project can be used as demonstrators and training devices for different applications in the future.</p>
Covered area/industrial sector	Manufacturing and assembly work
Manufacturer/provider	Institute of Innovation and Industrial Management at Graz University of Technology Corresponding author: Matthias Wolf, matthias.wolf@tugraz.at , +433168737796
Market availability	Not applicable
Indicative cost	Not applicable
Licence	Not applicable
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sensory ability <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical ability Musculoskeletal disorders <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) Stress sensation
Domain/type of solution	<p><u>Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To adapt work environment to aging functional decline • To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases
Need of training to use the solution	Yes, the technology is used mainly for training purposes

Results and benefits	<p>The course at the IIM LEAD Factory should start with a first practical experience of assembling the products in the LEAD factory, accompanied with basic theoretical knowledge about age-related changes of human abilities and their influence on the perceived strain level. With the new information acquired about increasing strain with rising age, the participants start to develop an understanding of the potential link that exists between workload and worker's abilities and limitations. In an additional practical phase, participants gain hands-on experience by either using an age simulation suit or being confronted with a higher workload. By doing this, either the job demands are increased which leads to a higher perceived strain or the worker's abilities are decreased which leads to the same worker's perception. As a result, participants are forced to self-experience the stresses and strains that can have an effect on the body's physical and psychological reactions. The participants can also experience potential outcomes of cost cutting initiatives such as reducing non-value adding time and breaks within the learning factory, by decreasing the cycle times or by working in bad environmental conditions as bad lightning or forced disturbances. Thereby, participants feel the effects of work stresses themselves and realize how stress can affect their own and other's job performance. During the different work tasks, some parameters that describe the physical stress level (e.g., the heart rate) can be monitored using any smart device like fitness trackers or smart clothing, and the perceived strain can be assessed by using tools like the BORG scale. This data along with the experience can be used in a wrap-up of the course to show relations between workers age, possible impairment and the work strain.</p>
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	Not applicable
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	easyfaM
Short description	Platform with various instructions and trainings on how to reconcile family (with children) and work and how to create family-friendly company structures.
Covered area/industrial sector	All
Manufacturer/provider	easyfaM GmbH & Co. KG Fridolin-Holzer-Straße 6, 88161 Lindenberg im Allgäu +49 8381 8307101 www.easyfam.com
Market availability	Yes www.easyfam.com
Indicative cost	The Parent Training Portal: 144 € per year For employers: no public information available
Licence	See above
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	X Learning, cognitive functions Methods and strategies to reconcile work and family life and to avoid stress caused by this are taught. Guidance on creating family-friendly company structures and avoiding 'family stress' and improving work performance.
Domain/type of solution	Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity programs tools • New therapies Yoga, Taichi, Mindfulness • Leisure programs Domain 4 Healthy habits programs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leisure and sleep educational programs The concept fits best in the domains mentioned above. However, it is aimed less at older employees and more at younger or middle-aged people with (small) children.
Need of training to use the solution	Yes

<p>Results and benefits</p>	<p>Promised potentials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parent employees return earlier & stay longer • More applicants as family-friendly is a decision criterion • Absenteeism significantly reduced • Employees learn working methodology & communication in their spare time • More women in career • Higher diversity in leadership / management • Fewer sick days • More time for professional commitment • Better performance with the existing workforce <p>Family stress keeps many employees away from careers. Create better conditions with the help of easyfaM®. Family stress leads to more sick days. The right methods for the family significantly reduce the causes. Agile tools for families relieve working parents. They therefore have more energy and time. easyfaM® tools bring modern working methods into family life in a playful way and with great success. The parents proudly bring these positive experiences to the company. Many fears of change dissolve. = more innovation, speed and profitability</p>
<p>Technical limitation or applicability limitations</p>	<p>So far available in German, EN coming soon.</p>
<p>Interoperability with other solution</p>	<p>Probably yes. Many of the concepts, even those that relate more to the private sphere, have similarities to common management or working methods or are based on them.</p>

Name of the application or technology	N.I.Te
Short description	<p>N.I.Te provides innovative software technologies for automatic document processing, especially handwritten documents, both off-line from static images, and on-line from handwriting coordinates acquired by several devices.</p> <p>Three main products:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Masquerade - a software for the analysis and the evaluation of morphological and dynamic features of handwriting. The software is tailored for handwriting experts, both from forensic and HR sectors, and is able to automatically measure handwritten features and reduce the time needed to produce a report. 2. HandBiblio - a software for indexing and searching by keywords in handwritten documents contained in huge digital archives (modern or historical). The software is particularly recommended for libraries, professional firms, private companies and public institutions that need to manage their digital heritage. HandBiblio is also quickly customizable on any dataset of words, and is able to learn from a reduced dataset of samples, obtaining a reduction on time and cost for the customers. 3. ApPost - a software for extracting and automatically obtaining information from digital documents, mainly handwritten ones. The software is able to automatically process structured and not structured documents by reading numeric and alphabetic fields and also handwritten words, not provided to the system during the learning step, by dynamically changing and quickly updating the lexicon, if required
Covered area/industrial sector	Any sector where handwriting could be used and processed, e.g.: Cyber security, Handwriting analysis, Legal/HR sector, Postal Sector, Insurance & Banking, Healthcare Regulation Sector, Cultural Heritage, Public Libraries, Private companies
Manufacturer/provider	<p>Natural Intelligent Technologies (N.I.Te)</p> <p>Piazza Vittorio Emanuele, 10 84084 Penta, Fisciano (SA) Italia info@nitesrl.com +39 089 96 8194</p>
Market availability	Yes http://www.nitesrl.com/
Indicative cost	Not provided
Licence	Natural Intelligent Technologies (N.I.Te)
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Sensory ability – in case of vision problems, any text could be translated into digital format, and adjusted <input type="checkbox"/> Physical ability <input type="checkbox"/> Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems)
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 1: Policy for older workers

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers. • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity programs tools • New therapies Yoga, Taichi, Mindfulness • Leisure programs • Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To adapt work environment to aging functional decline • To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases
Need of training to use the solution	Yes
Results and benefits	Information not available
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	Only for digital tool users Only English and Italian language version available
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (not sure) how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	DearEmployee
Short description	<p>DearEmployee is a corporate health platform that supports companies in creating healthy and motivating working conditions for their employees (mental health focus).</p> <p>Using the DearEmployee platform, companies can easily and digitally measure mental stress at the workplace, and subsequently sign up to tailored health and HR measures. However, planning tailored health and HR measures is a consultancy-like process, which is paid additionally (not a digital automatic tool).</p> <p>The solution also meets the legal requirements for mental health risk assessment in Germany.</p> <p>DearEmployee consists of online survey, workplace analytics and measure planning. In addition to the functionalities already deployed, DearEmployee introduces new online survey measuring mental health of employees in relation to the COVID-19 pandemic and proposes adequate measures, e.g. solutions for managing staff working from home, as well as advice in the areas of occupational safety and occupational medicine, e.g. to ensure adequate implementation of hygiene standards. (CoronaCare Survey, in German only)</p>
Covered area/industrial sector	<p>General, although access to electronic devices is necessary to take part in the online survey</p> <p>Customized to any industry or company size</p>
Manufacturer/provider	<p>info@dearemployee.de</p> <p>Dr. Amelie Wiedemann - Co-Founder & Chief Scientific Officer</p> <p>Henning Jakob - Co-Founder & CEO</p> <p>Daniel Fodor - Co-Founder & COO</p>
Market availability	Yes dearemployee.com
Indicative cost	<p>Basic – 1,5 € per employee/month</p> <p>Plus – 2 € per employee/month</p> <p>Premium – 4 € per employee/month</p>
Licence	DearEmployee
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) – online survey is devoted to analysing mental health of workers and stress risk and subsequently actions towards improvement in this area can be proposed</p>

Domain/type of solution	<p>Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity programs tools • New therapies Yoga, Taichi, Mindfulness • Leisure programs <p>Domain 4 Healthy habits programs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrition • Physical activity • Leisure and sleep educational programs • Vaccines and medical check (early prevention programs)
Need of training to use the solution	No
Results and benefits	Not available
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	English and German language version (Only German language available on the CoronaCare)
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No

Name of the application or technology	Userlane
Short description	Userlane is a no-code Digital Adoption Platform that is designed to maximize software adoption by allowing anyone to master any software instantly. This is made possible with a step-by-step interactive guidance technology and on-demand Virtual Assistant that offers contextual and tailored support to software users whenever they need it. This solution can be used both for employee onboarding and training (enterprise digital adoption) as well as customer onboarding and self-service (for software vendors). The step-by-step, on-screen interactive guides lead users through digital processes in any browser-based software in real-time. It supports learning new software.
Covered area/industrial sector	Any industry using software
Manufacturer/provider	Userlane info@userlane.com; Phone Number +49414171171 www.userlane.com
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	Custom pricing (Userlane has not provided pricing information)
Licence	Userlane
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions – it supports employees in learning new software
Domain/type of solution	<p>Domain 1: Policy for older workers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability • Domain 5: Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms
Need of training to use the solution	No, the solution is the training programme
Results and benefits	No information
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	Languages Supported: German, English, French, Italian, Spanish, Chinese (Simplified)
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No (not sure) Any browser-based software

Annex III: Apps and tools analysed

Name of the best practice	Comfy / SafeWorkspace
Short description	Manages office presence of employees in COVID-19 times
Covered area/industrial sector	Office management
Promoter	Building Robotics Inc., Siemens
Indicative cost	Not available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Workability
Domain/type of solution	<p>Domain 1: Policy for older workers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers. <p>Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning and training tools and technologies <p>Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physical activity programs tools New therapies Yoga, Taichi, Mindfulness Leisure programs
Need of training to implement the motivational approach or/and the best practice	No training needed, motivation is intrinsic to stay healthy
Results and benefits of the	People involved is around 140.000 users in Germany, Austria and Switzerland
Applicability limitations	Only available for offices and setup is needed to configure each office room / building in accordance with COVID-19 regulations

Name of the application or technology	BlogIn
Short description	BlogIn is a simple internal blog and knowledge sharing platform for teams of all sizes. Internal blog is a perfect tool to share internal news, archive knowledge, boost collaboration and improve internal communication For features: https://blogin.co/features
Covered area/industrial sector	All sectors
Manufacturer/provider	Who is the provider of the technology? Contact info https://blogin.co
Market availability	yes
Indicative cost	39\$/month 390\$/year
Licence	If available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	Workability
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 1: Policy for older workers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers.</u>
Need of training to use the solution	No
Results and benefits	Boosts collaboration and improves internal communication. Makes workplace more friendly to the employees Increases productivity Encourages people to speak up
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	
Interoperability with other solution	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	Muscle & Motion
Short description	<p>It is a professional app for acquiring advanced knowledge on strength training, stretching anatomy and posture during yoga learning how to prevent common mistakes in order to reduce risk of injury (including concrete reasons for why these mistakes occur), and deeply understanding the anatomy of all human muscles in the most visual way.</p> <p>This advanced app enables user to look “under the skin” in 3D form.</p> <p>Main help in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Learning to train in a safe way and minimize the risk of injury + Understanding the way muscles move and interact during training
Covered area/industrial sector	General
Manufacturer/provider	<p>Who is the provider of the technology? Contact info</p> <p>sales@muscleandmotion.com</p> <p>Muscle&Motion Ltd</p> <p>Tel Aviv, Israel</p>
Market availability	<p>Yes</p> <p>Google play:</p> <p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=air.com.muscleemotion.strength.mobile&hl=pl&gl=US</p> <p>App store</p> <p>https://apps.apple.com/pl/app/anatomy-by-muscle-motion/id1149322730?l=pl</p> <p>PC</p> <p>https://www.muscleandmotion.com/</p>
Indicative cost	<p>It depends on application version</p> <p>The Strength Training App: \$149 per 3 years, \$60 per year or \$15 per month</p> <p>The Posture App: \$396 per 3 years, \$149 per year or \$30 per month</p> <p>The Strength Training App includes the Anatomy App content. (2 in 1)</p> <p>The Posture App includes the Yoga App content & the Anatomy App content. (3 in 1)</p> <p>There is also a free version but it gives access only to 25 % of their educational videos.</p>
Licence	If available

Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions Application can help to understand the way muscles move and interact during training and learn to train in a safe way as well as minimize the risk of injury. <input type="checkbox"/> Physical ability Application can help to understand the way muscles move and interact during training and learn to train in a safe way as well as minimize the risk of injury.
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity programs tools • New therapies Yoga, • Leisure programs • Domain 4 Healthy habits programs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity
Need of training to use the solution	No, with basic smartphone/apps usage knowledge
Results and benefits	Not available
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	In general, exercises should be done at home because the person should be focused on it and prepared (appropriate clothing).
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Name of the application or technology	Diet&Training by Ann
Short description	Diet & Training by Ann Lewandowska is an individually tailored fit diet and simple training. Simple diet - the person chooses what to eat. Training plan for everyone - exercises on various difficulty levels.
Covered area/industrial sector	General
Manufacturer/provider	DietLabs sp. z o.o. sp.k. contact@healthyplanbyann.com DietLabs Sp. z o. o. sp. k ul. Chełmońskiego 8/4 60-758 Poznań
Market availability	Yes https://apps.apple.com/pl/app/dieta-i-treningi-by-ann/id1142970408?l=pl https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.apzumi.mobile.dietlabs.dietByAnn&hl=pl&gl=US https://dieta.hpba.pl/nowyrok/?gclid=Cj0KCQjA9iBBhCJARIsAE9qRtDTUAgoZo4KCh36faCrXuWk5Me2hFGqpMOI7LK1du5m6cKobZqiyoMaAtDAEALw_wcB
Indicative cost	8,49 USD-59,99 USD per element Approximately 150 USD for lifetime access
Licence	DietLabs sp. z o.o. sp.k.
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Physical ability - The application contains a collection of training programs that can be adapted to user abilities and skills, for people of all ages (e.g. full body cardio, Yoga, barbell workouts, body combo, strong core). The application also has diet options with the possibility of individual adjustment – including shopping list. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hydration, body shape and progress <input type="checkbox"/> Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) – The application includes breathing exercise options and balance functions filled with recordings straight from the world of nature and original, relaxing music
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity programs tools • New therapies Yoga, Mindfulness • Leisure programs • Domain 4 Healthy habits programs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrition • Physical activity • Leisure and sleep educational programs

Need of training to use the solution	No (with basic knowledge of using smartphones/apps)
Results and benefits	Information not available
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	<p>Compatibility</p> <p>iPhone Requires iOS 12.0 or later.</p> <p>iPad Requires iPadOS 12.0 or later.</p> <p>iPod touch Requires iOS 12.0 or later.</p> <p>Mac Requires macOS 11 or later and a Mac with an Apple M1 chip.</p> <p>Android 5.0 or later.</p> <p>https://apps.apple.com/pl/app/dieta-i-treningi-by-ann/id1142970408?l=pl Language – Polish, English, German</p> <p>https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.apzumi.mobile.dietlabs.dietByAnn&hl=pl&gl=US Language – Polish, no data available on other languages</p>
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, with Google Fit

Name of the application or technology	Neuropil
Short description	<p>https://www.neuropil.org/tutorial/core_concepts.html</p> <p>The Neuropil layer is an open source solution that assures the stable communication between machines and applications. It is a c-library, which is locally installed and embedded into a company's own application or devices. The lean messaging library is developed with two layers of encryption (transport and end-to-end) and it gives each system a digital entity to avoid unauthorized access. The exchange of data between IoT devices and applications is dynamic, decentralized and fully automated. It provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic discovery of data channels across enterprises • Attribute based access control to authorize data exchange • Asymmetric end-to-end encryption between the participating systems • Protection of IoT devices regarding excessive payloads • High scalability without central infrastructure • Centralized governance, but decentralized messaging
Covered area/industrial sector	In organizations dealing with highly sensitive information, like the healthcare industry.
Manufacturer/provider	<p>www.pi-lar.net</p> <p>info@pi-lar.net</p> <p>+49.221.16531700</p>
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	Not available
Licence	OSL 3.0
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	Transversal
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>To adapt work environment to aging functional decline</u> • <u>To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases</u>
Need of training to use the solution	Yes
Results and benefits	The Neuropil® layer ensures data quality, data transparency, and data sovereignty all that while reducing IT costs, maximizing availability, and increasing reliability.
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	

Interoperability other solution	with <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners
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Name of the application or technology	PIPEFORCE
Short description	PIPEFORCE is an easy-to-use and freely scalable platform based on Kubernetes in order to be able to develop, link and automate business workflows uniformly in a container environment. With this platform, companies can migrate their services step by step. The platform offers the following functionalities:- Modelling of workflows graphically and putting them into operation immediately- Creating forms and business apps - Revolutionary data integration with messaging and RPA -Management of cloud services centrally and link them with on-premises - Over 1,000 ready-made interfaces and workflow templates, -Integrated archive / DMS, reporting, ETL etc.
Covered area/industrial sector	Construction industry, production, commerce, transport, insurances
Manufacturer/provider	Logabit GmbH, Agnes-Pockels-Bogen 1 80992 München +49 89 244 187 46 – 0 office@logabit.com
Market availability	YES
Indicative cost	Not available
Licence	If available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 1: Policy for older workers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers.</u> • <u>Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>To adapt work environment to aging functional decline</u> • To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases
Need of training to use the solution	Yes
Results and benefits	Manual process effort in the construction industry can be reduced by 60%. Process runtimes in production lines can be reduced by more than 80%.
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	It is fully cloud-native (microservices, independent from any IaaS provider) and therefore unlimitedly scalable. It provides RPA (Robotic Process Automation), intelligent Business Process Management (iBPMN), Rules Engine, Data/API Integration and Enterprise Business Services on a central cloud platform. Additionally, it connects any of these features with a neural network and semantic model (AI/ML)
Interoperability with other solution	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	Smartfence
Short description	<p>Smartfence is an Information Security training and awareness platform that develops safe habits for end users. It offers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment tools (Phishing and Ransomware simulation components, surveys, exams) • Education and reinforcement tools (Game-based learning, interactive modules) • Measurement tools • Audit and compliance tools • Scheduling tools
Covered area/industrial sector	All sectors
Manufacturer/provider	<p>SMARTFENCE Salta 182 2400 San Francisco, Córdoba, Argentina +549 3564 63 87 58 sales@smartfence.com</p>
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	Not available
Licence	If available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement)</u> • <u>Learning and training tools and technologies</u>
Need of training to use the solution	Yes
Results and benefits	<p>Risk incidents reduction Better acceptance of management</p>
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	Not known
Interoperability with other solution	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	SmartWe
Short description	It is an app-based CRM Cloud solution for small and medium-sized companies with the following features: Contact and task management, central document storage, customer history, team calendar, personalized forms of address for documents and e-mails all of which can be created in record time
Covered area/industrial sector	All sectors.
Manufacturer/provider	Web page: https://smartwe.de/en/service-2-2/ Tel. number: +49 721 9638-555 Email: info@SmartWe.World
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	SmartWe Starter: 9,90€/net/user/month SmartWe Team: 19,90€/net/user/month SmartWe Premium: 29,90€/net/user/month
Licence	If available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions Team work, time and task management <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) Team work, time and task management
Domain/type of solution	Domain 1: Policy for older workers <u>Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers.</u>
Need of training to use the solution	Yes
Results and benefits	Contact management with intelligent wizards. Appointment management and team calendar. Fan principle for customers. Personal relationship manager
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	Runs with internet browser based on the HTML 5 standard. Overview of recommended internet browsers here . Overview of recommended operating systems here . At least a DSL Internet connection is needed.
Interoperability with other solution	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	Spatial
Short description	<p>Spatial is an AR workspaces app. In AR mode, the spatial mobile app allows users to beam avatars of their friends or team-mates right into their living room to collaborate in the real space around you.</p> <p>How does Spatial work?</p> <p>Create a lifelike avatar and work as if next to each other.</p> <p>Transform your room into your monitor and then fill it with information.</p> <p>Use all of your favorite existing tools so your workflow remains intact.</p> <p>And use any device, including VR/AR headsets, your desktop, or your phone to participate.</p>
Covered area/industrial sector	All sectors
Manufacturer/provider	hello@spatial.io
Market availability	yes
Indicative cost	<p>Free</p> <p>Pro: 20\$/user/month</p> <p>Enterprise: after contact</p>
Licence	If available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Workability
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Domain 1: Policy for older workers</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers.</u> • <u>Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To adapt work environment to aging functional decline • <u>To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases</u>
Need of training to use the solution	No
Results and benefits	
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	<p>App for iOS and Android that runs on almost any current generation of mobile device.</p> <p>Oculus quest, Hololens, MagicLeap, Nreal Beta, Web, iOS, Android</p>
Interoperability with other solution	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	TrackLean
Short description	TrackLean is a Software as a Service (SaaS) solution for the electronic signing of contract documents online. ²
Covered area/industrial sector	
Manufacturer/provider	Solutiance Systems GmbH Wetzlarer Straße 50 14482 Potsdam Tel.: +49-331-867193-61 info@solutiance.com
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	Not available
Licence	If available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Domain 1: Policy for older workers</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers.</u>
Need of training to use the solution	Probably not
Results and benefits	Less paper, fast execution of electronic signature, safely archived files.
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	TrackLean is compatible with current versions of the following browsers: Microsoft Edge, Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome, Opera, Safari, as well as all mobile variants of the mentioned browsers.
Interoperability with other solution	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

² This tool is not directly related to the technological development of the Ageing@Work technological development, however it is included in this benchmark since the increasing digitalization process of manufacturing and logistic process. Technologies and tools like this one, can contribute to the digitalization of small and familiar companies that work without digital support, and in this way for further development of the system

Name of the application or technology	Valarea
Short description	<p>It is a visual collaboration software that enables sharing, noting and presenting digital content in real-time from any device. Projects can be organized in folders called “workspaces”, allowing to archive and sync files, media and meeting sessions on all devices. Each collaborative meeting session starts with a blank page called “canvas”. All users that are participating can present their content and enrich it with annotations, while revising the daily tasks or any other information relevant to the meeting. At the end of each meeting, a brief wizard will guide the user through the steps of creating a highly personalised recap, which can be archived in a workspace or shared with all or some of the participants. There is also integrated file manager.</p> <p>Valarea POD is an extension to the Valarea App, ideal for meeting room displays that can be utilized as Wireless Presentation tools, collaboration tools and AV conference tools.</p>
Covered area/industrial sector	All sectors
Manufacturer/provider	Re Mago Ltd info@remago.com
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	Free use and basic and premium use with subscriptions. Cost is not available
Licence	Yes
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Domain 1: Policy for older workers</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers.</u>
Need of training to use the solution	Yes
Results and benefits	<p>Save over 10 minutes per meeting</p> <p>Increase meeting productivity by 25%</p> <p>Enhance collaboration</p>
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	<p>Valarea POD for Windows</p> <p>Minimum version: Windows 10 (build 1809)</p> <p>Valarea for iOS (iPhone / iPad)</p> <p>Minimum version: iOS 11.3</p> <p>Valarea for Android</p> <p>Minimum version: Android 7.0</p>
Interoperability with other solution	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	LabsLand
Short description	LabsLand connects users (schools, universities and individual users) with real laboratories available somewhere else on the Internet. In real-time laboratories students access the equipment at the same time things are happening. Ultra-concurrent laboratories are based on a set of pre-recorded experiences carried out at a real lab. Then, the ultra-concurrent laboratory interface allows the user to have the same experience as in a real-time laboratory.
Covered area/industrial sector	Higher education, schools
Manufacturer/provider	Weblab-Deusto Contact form only available at website https://labsland.com
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	Standard: 4,99€/student/term Advanced: 9,99€/student/term
Licence	No
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement)</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Learning and training tools and technologies</u>
Need of training to use the solution	Probably not
Results and benefits	Experiential learning
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	Not available
Interoperability with other solution	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	Validated ID - VIDSigner
Short description	<p>VIDsigner ³(one of the Validated ID solutions) is an electronic signature service suitable for both face-to-face and remote situations, combining cryptography and biometrics to offer a secure way to electronically sign documents and contracts with full legal validity.</p> <p>Special importance in the COVID-19 pandemic where personal contact is not advised, thus it can increase safety of employees. Also, useful for remote workers.</p> <p>Two other solutions are VIDChain (decentralized self-rule identity (SSI) service based on Blockchain to provide people control over their identity and facilitate secure user access to online services) and SP4i electronic invoice.</p> <p>Works as an app (Android, iOS, Windows) and PC version</p>
Covered area/industrial sector	Any industry
Manufacturer/provider	<p>Validated ID</p> <p>C/ Aragó 179, 4th floor</p> <p>08011 Barcelona</p> <p>Tel: +34 900 828 948</p>
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	No information
Licence	No information
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/> Physical ability – enables remote work and could be treated as a way to protect physical health (keeping social distance in COVID-19 pandemic)
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical activity programs tools • New therapies Yoga, Taichi, Mindfulness • Leisure programs • To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases
Need of training to use the solution	Yes
Results and benefits	Potentially, it could protect physical health while also improving efficiency
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	<p>Laws and regulations vary, but VIDsigner's electronic signatures are designed to comply with most electronic signature laws worldwide, from Regulation (EU) 910/2014 (EIDAS) to the E-SIGN and UETA laws in the United States.</p> <p>VIDSigner Bio (face-to-face signature procedure) works with</p>

³ This tool is not directly related to the technological development of the Ageing@Work technological development, however it is included in this benchmark since the increasing digitalization process of manufacturing and logistic process. Technologies and tools like this one, can contribute to the digitalization of small

	<p>Homologated tablets. VIDSigner Remote (Remote with Certificate) works with PC/Smartphone/Tablet Certificates (both face-to-face and remote with certificate) works with PC/Smartphone/Tablet</p>
<p>Interoperability with other solution</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No VIDsigner is a service designed to be integrated into third-party solutions. Integration: API Rest Integrated with: SAP, Microsoft, Salesforce, DocuWare, Sage</p>

Name of the application or technology	Files.fm
Short description	Cloud storage and synchronizing tool with the following features: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Document management and remote access - Tools to sell digital downloads or views and receive payments - Publication of photos to allow event participants to find their pictures - Windows/Linux private server rental for business - Encrypted file back up for computers and servers - File upload form from websites
Covered area/industrial sector	All sectors
Manufacturer/provider	Files.fm LTD The Innovation Centre Sci-Tech Daresbury Keckwick Lane Daresbury WA4 4FS, UK E-mail: support@files.fm
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	Basic user: free PRO features: 2TB: 9,9€/month, 250GB: 4,9€/month Business for teams: 10€/month File upload form: 9,9€/month
Licence	If available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	Transversal
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 1: <u>Policy for older workers</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers.</u>
Need of training to use the solution	No
Results and benefits	
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	Windows/MacOS, android, WebDAV network drive
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	OpenClassrooms
Short description	Online education platform for vocational training, providing courses in IT, technology, entrepreneurship, and digital skills
Covered area/industrial sector	All industrial sectors
Manufacturer/provider	Cibervoluntarios.org Address: Calle Pedro Unanue 14, local - 28045, Madrid (España) Email: fundacion@cibervoluntarios.org Phone No.: +34 91 542 29 00
Market availability	Yes, https://www.cibervoluntarios.org/en/join-us
Indicative cost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Free membership (limited to 5 courses per week) - Premium Solo membership costing €20 per month (access to unlimited videos as well as earn certificates) - Premium Plus membership costing from €300 per month (follow a structured learning path consisting of projects, dedicated mentoring sessions and a state-endorsed degree at the end)
Licence	
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	X Learning, cognitive functions Further training for ageing workers
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies
Need of training to use the solution	Depending on the training, no prior knowledge required
Results and benefits	OpenClassrooms offers 1000+ courses focusing on in-demand skills and ranging from entrepreneurship, digital marketing to web development. Since 2015, OpenClassrooms also offers what it calls learning paths. A learning path relies on real-life projects and mentorship. Additionally, students have access to courses within modules in order to get all the resources that they need. At the end of each module, the student is asked to complete a project that is then assessed by a mentor. When students have completed all their projects, their work is assessed by a jury. If the session is successful, students are then awarded with an internationally recognized diploma.
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	Jobs@Skills
Short description	Platform for further training measures
Covered area/industrial sector	Further education for all industrial sectors
Manufacturer/provider	Atrium Vertbois Rue du Vertbois, 11 B-4000 Lüttich Tel: +32 (0) 4 263 14 08
Market availability	Yes, www.jobsatskills.be
Indicative cost	
Licence	
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	X Learning, cognitive functions Further training of ageing workers
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies
Need of training to use the solution	Depending on the training, no prior knowledge
Results and benefits	Develop workers skills thanks to the training courses developed by different partners universities, higher education institutions, training centres & companies.
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	LifeSignals Biosensor 1AX
Short description	Wireless medical biosensors and a COVID-19 Personal Symptom Monitoring App
Covered area/industrial sector	All types of industrial sector
Manufacturer/provider	LifeSignals Europe IDA Business & Technology Park, Garrycastle, Dublin Rd, Athlone, Co Westmeath, N37 F786, Ireland Tel: +353 90 646 5460, +44 7710 532963 info@lifesignals.com
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	Only on request
Licence	If available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	X Physical ability People can place the biosensor patch on their chest. The biosensor is linked with a smart phone app and allows for continuous monitoring for COVID-19 symptoms.
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 1: Policy for older workers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers. • Domain 4 Healthy habits programs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrition • Physical activity • Leisure and sleep educational programs • Vacuums and medical check (early prevention programs) • Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To adapt work environment to aging functional decline • To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases
Need of training to use the solution	Easy to use, no special knowledge needed. The app shows and tracks the vital signs in real-time, using easy to follow traffic light charts. The app provides health trends and alerts so the person can contact their healthcare provider if required
Results and benefits	<p>For many people who are currently self-isolated at home, continuous monitoring of COVID-19 symptoms is not possible. With the Biosensor 1AX and Symptom Tracking App, key COVID-19 symptoms can be continually monitored, providing individuals with detailed health trends and alerts. The collective symptom real-time data can be used by health authorities to assess the health status of mass-population enabling resources to be effectively targeted.</p> <p>Individuals can self apply the biosensor which is paired with the App on their smart phone. The App will display and track measurements using user-friendly traffic light charts. A 5-day summary in PDF format, can be emailed via the secure cloud platform for referrals. Concerned family members or</p>

	carers can remotely monitor isolated seniors or vulnerable persons without increasing cross infection risk. If symptoms change, an alert is raised and the user can quickly contact their healthcare service for advice. User's cumulative vital sign data can be monitored to identify geographical COVID-19 hotspots, assisting resource allocation.
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	HRCOFFEE
Short description	Digital HR-Management, bottom-up management of people and knowledge Digital workplace that connects all employees of a company with a bottom-up, smart and dynamic approach. It focuses on employee's actions that translate into useful insights for management and strategic business development
Covered area/industrial sector	Small and medium enterprises, large companies and public administration
Manufacturer/provider	HRCOFFEE via Adriano Olivetti, 11 70056 Molfetta (BA) +39 3273475518 http://www.hrcoffee.it/en
Market availability	Yes http://www.hrcoffee.it/en
Indicative cost	No information available
Licence	No information available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	X Learning, cognitive functions (<i>fits most closely</i>) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People analytics & comparative analysis • Project & smart working • Adaptive learning • Competence gap analysis • Skills mapping
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies • Domain 3: Improving productivity and workability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.palgrave.com/gp/book/9781137585349 • https://www.palgrave.com/gp/book/9783319602097 • https://www.palgrave.com/gp/book/9781137410788
Need of training to use the solution	No information, probably yes
Results and benefits	The HRCOFFEE platform and application give the opportunity to digitize business processes through innovative systems of social collaboration, people analytics, coffee recruiting, evaluation, contests and peer to peer training.

Technical limitation or applicability limitations	No information
Interoperability with other solution	No information <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Name of the application or technology	cidaas
Short description	Cloud identity and access management
Covered area/industrial sector	Bank, E-Commerce, Healthcare, Education, Government, Industry 4.0, Sports
Manufacturer/provider	Widas ID GmbH Maybachstraße 2 71299 Wimsheim Tel: +49(0)7044 95103-200 E-mail: sales@cidaas.de https://www.cidaas.com
Market availability	Yes
Indicative cost	Ranges from free Version, cidaas Essentials (499 € monthly), cidaas Standard (999 € monthly), cidaas Pro (2899 € monthly) to cidaas Enterprise (price on request) https://www.cidaas.com/pricing-packages/
Licence	Software is available in 5 service packages (see 'Indicative cost') and smartphone app: https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.cidaas.authenticator&hl=de https://apps.apple.com/us/app/cidaasauthenticator/id1199864806
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	Transversal
Domain/type of solution	Classification not possible here, these are solutions for cloud identity and access management.
Need of training to use the solution	No information available

<p>Results and benefits</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multifactor authentication • Consent management • Physical access control • ID Validation • Password-less authentication • Access management • Single Sign-On (SSO) • API-Security and API management • Fraud and anomaly detection • Social login & registration • User de-duplication • Password management • Individual protection of all channels of your company • Device management • E-mail opt in • Client specific custom fields in user data • User self-services • Secure portals and Web-APIs by using OAuth2 -Keyword PSD2 • cidaas B2B – Expand and secure customer base many folds • Real world Identification
<p>Technical limitation or applicability limitations</p>	<p>No information available</p>
<p>Interoperability with other solution</p>	<p>X Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>cidaas can be seamlessly integrated into your software environment. As a service, cidaas offers scalability, security, transparency, and flexibility so you can focus on your core business. The list of Social Providers cidaas currently supports:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amazon • Facebook • Foursquare • GitHub • GooglePlus • Google G suite • Instagram • LinkedIn • Microsoft (Live) • Microsoft Office365 • PayPal • Salesforce • Twitter • WordPress

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Yahoo If additional social providers are wanted, they can easily be added. <p>Optional Integration into existing AD/LDAP systems.</p>
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Name of the application or technology	Precise COVID-19
Short description	Remote patients monitoring and clinical decision support for healthcare providers with COVID-19 patients
Covered area/industrial sector	All industrial sectors
Manufacturer/provider	BESURE Healthcare B.V. 2 Louis Couperusplein 2514 HP, The Hague, Netherlands
Market availability	Yes, https://www.cibervoluntarios.org/en/join-us
Indicative cost	Free
Licence	
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	X Physical ability Accurate and timely identification of COVID-19 symptoms
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 4 Healthy habits programs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrition • Physical activity • Leisure and sleep educational programs • Vacuums and medical check (early prevention programs)
Need of training to use the solution	Wearable with no need of training for patients, analysis done by medical experts
Results and benefits	Accurate and timely identification of patients at high risk of cardiovascular and respiratory complications and hard cases. Diagnostics and monitoring of side effects, cardiac dysfunctions and complications. 24/7 remote patients monitoring, analytics and clinical decision support during recovery and rehabilitation.
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	Walkie
Short description	It enables quick communication with co-workers via real time voice chat and allows leaving messages across different applications.
Covered area/industrial sector	All type of industrial sector possible
Manufacturer/provider	https://www.walkie.chat/ hey@walkie.chat
Market availability	No, still under development
Indicative cost	(if not available commercially, indicate cost of the pilot application)
Licence	If available
Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)	X Learning, cognitive functions communication with co-workers via real time voice chat X Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) Allows ageing workers to work from home during COVID-19 pandemic
Domain/type of solution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 1: Policy for older workers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers. • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies • Domain 5 Adaptation and compensatory mechanisms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To adapt work environment to aging functional decline • To adapt work environment to chronic illness or diseases
Need of training to use the solution	Easy to use
Results and benefits	<p>This is useful for faster communication, decision-making, having fewer meetings and understanding the voice tone of the sender of the message better which improves mutual understanding.</p> <p>This technology is specifically beneficial for ageing workers for several reasons. Firstly, it is specifically useful for an ageing worker who may have trouble typing messages fast due to dexterity issues or who simply forgot their reading glasses. Instant voice chat can resolve this issue instantly. Secondly, verbal fluency remains at a high functional level until advanced ages, therefore the use of digital voice notes benefits especially ageing workers. Thirdly, for lower educated older workers the transition to digital technology by using voice notes rather than requiring to type notes will potentially increase acceptance of such technology at a faster rate and thereby their employability.</p>
Technical limitation or applicability limitations	
Interoperability with other solution	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No how? This will be checked after with WP4 and WP5 partners

Name of the application or technology	plazz AG Mobile Employee App
Short description	<p>The plazz AG Mobile Employee App targets the digitalization of internal communication among the employer and its employees, supporting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Precise distribution of information • Creating inclusion and solidarity amongst colleagues • High degree of individualization • 24/7 on employees' smartphones <p>The app works on Android, iOS and web browsers. It is based on modular building blocks of content. The following use cases are covered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team-App: Communication of shift schedules, optimization suggestions, between colleagues or as a knowledge base. • Preboarding-App: To bridge the time between contract signing and first workday with relevant information. • Onboarding-App: Provides your new employees with a successful and structured start into the company. • Academy-App: For internal further education, training courses, transfer of knowledge and talent programs. • Field-Staff-App: Exchange with headquarters about new products and additional information.
Covered area/industrial sector	The app is not specific to a predetermined area or an industrial sector.
Manufacturer/provider	<p>plazz AG Web: https://mobile-employee-app.com/ Mail: sales@plazz.ag Phone: +49 (0) 89 809 23 656</p>
Market availability	Yes, available at the contacts above mentioned
Indicative cost	<p>The MEA price structure is composed of two basic components: setup fee and event license. Quotations are available on request, classified in the following packages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small: 100 users • Medium: 500 users • Large: 1,000 users • Volume: more than 1,000 users
Licence	Yes

<p>Problem addressed (explain specifically how addressed the problem)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Learning, cognitive functions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The app supports distribution of information, instruction materials, agenda planning, floorplan mapping (including geolocated content), etc. • The app supports employee communication, including chats, push messages (including for motivation and engagement) and news, wall of ideas, etc. <input type="checkbox"/> Psychology/Mental abilities (including sleep problems) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gamification and quizzes are available to support employees' motivation
<p>Domain/type of solution</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain 1: Policy for older workers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools and technologies aimed at improving interpersonal communication between the latter and other workplace workers. • Domain 2: Increasing job retention (postponing early retirement) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and training tools and technologies
<p>Need of training to use the solution</p>	<p>Training courses, webinars and documents to help customers prepare for the use of the app are made available by the provider.</p>
<p>Results and benefits</p>	<p>The app can be used universally for all staff, or it can be specialized for apprentices, new employees or non-desk workers. Using the Mobile Employee App will help a company to improve employees' productivity. The app can also be used as a Multi-Experience-App, where multiple use cases can be addressed in different designs via a content management system. Every instance can be customized individually.</p>
<p>Technical limitation or applicability limitations</p>	<p>No specific limitations are reported by the provider.</p>
<p>Interoperability with other solution</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content can be imported. • Data on app usage can be exported and downloaded. Using the Matomo tool (https://matomo.org/) data collection can be controlled by the users (opt-in) to ensure privacy protection and can be collected in anonymized form. • A management API is available to integrate with customer's internal IT services (including exchange of information between databases). • Integration with third-party APIs is possible (e.g., Profile integration of XING and LinkedIn, display of social media feeds).